

1 Iron metabolism, hereditary hemochromatosis and 2 aluminum: pathogenic links in macrophagic myofasciitis 3 Review

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7 ABSTRACT

8 Macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF) is a chronic fatigue syndrome linked to aluminum present in
9 certain vaccines, where it is used as an adjuvant to enhance immune response. The primary
10 symptoms include cognitive impairments, chronic exhaustion and muscle and joint pain,
11 although other body systems may also be affected. The mechanisms underlying aluminum
12 accumulation in macrophages at the vaccination injection site suggest failures in the innate
13 immune system's cellular waste elimination processes.

14 Concurrently, dysregulation of iron metabolism is often observed in inflammatory and
15 metabolic syndromes. However, iron metabolism is also influenced by genetic factors,
16 particularly in hereditary hemochromatosis, a condition that leads to iron overload and various
17 organ damages. Symptoms such as chronic fatigue, joint pain, and liver and cardiac dysfunction
18 share similarities with those of MMF, pointing to potential pathophysiological overlaps.

19 Moreover, several studies have shown that aluminum can interfere with iron metabolism by
20 utilizing the same pathways for absorption, transport, and storage in the body. These findings
21 suggest that genetic alterations in iron metabolism, such as those observed in
22 hemochromatosis, could influence aluminum retention and accumulation in the body.

23 This raises an important question: could genetic polymorphisms affecting iron metabolism be
24 a determining factor in susceptibility to macrophagic myofasciitis?

25

26

27 **Keywords:**

28 Iron metabolism, Iron homeostasis, Aluminum toxicity, Macrophagic Myofasciitis, Genetic
 29 predisposition, Hemochromatosis, Ferroportin, TFR2 gene, SLC40A1 mutations,
 30 Environmental exposure, Neuroinflammation, Inflammatory diseases, Vaccine adjuvants,
 31 Review article.

32 **Genetic Susceptibility to Macrophagic Myofasciitis:**

33 **Hypothesis and Rationale**

34 Macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF) is a rare inflammatory disease associated with the
 35 persistence of aluminum-containing vaccine adjuvants in muscle macrophages. While
 36 aluminum overload has been clearly established in MMF pathogenesis, the underlying
 37 mechanisms that govern its accumulation and persistence remain incompletely understood.

38 Recent insights into the role of iron metabolism in inflammation and immunity suggest that
 39 dysregulation of iron pathways could contribute to altered macrophage function and impaired
 40 metal clearance. Furthermore, genetic factors, notably hereditary hemochromatosis and
 41 mutations affecting iron regulation genes, may influence susceptibility to metal accumulation,
 42 including aluminum.

43 This review aims to synthesize current knowledge on iron metabolism, hereditary
 44 hemochromatosis, and their interactions with aluminum metabolism, to explore a novel
 45 hypothesis: that genetic predispositions impacting iron homeostasis could facilitate aluminum
 46 retention and inflammatory responses in MMF.

47 To build this argument, we will first present a detailed overview of iron metabolism, review
 48 known genetic disruptions affecting iron handling, and then discuss aluminum's interactions
 49 with iron pathways. Finally, we will propose new perspectives for research and clinical
 50 management based on these emerging connections.

51 Iron metabolism: cellular regulation

52 Regulation of iron metabolism

53 To maintain a healthy body, iron levels are tightly regulated through a complex mechanism.
54 Iron is involved in numerous biochemical processes, such as oxygen transport, energy
55 production, and DNA synthesis. However, most of the iron is utilized in erythropoiesis, the
56 synthesis of red blood cells and hemoglobin. It also plays a role in the synthesis of myoglobin
57 in muscle cells and in detoxification mechanisms in the liver for the synthesis of cytochrome
58 P450 enzymes. [\[1, 2\]](#)

59 Iron stored in bone marrow is used to produce red blood cells. When red blood cells reach the
60 end of their lifespan, they are destroyed in the spleen through phagocytosis by macrophages.
61 Iron can then be stored in the ferritin of macrophages or released as needed by the body.
62 Released iron is taken up by transferrin, a transport protein. This recycling of iron serves as a
63 constant internal source of iron. [\[1, 2, 3\]](#)

64 The second source of iron is dietary. A fraction of dietary iron is absorbed by enterocytes via
65 the transport protein Divalent Metal Transporter 1 (DMT1). [\[1, 2, 3\]](#)

66 Intestinal iron absorption is regulated by hepcidin (encoded by the HFE gene), a key hormone
67 that controls the amount of iron absorbed and released into the body. Hepcidin is a protein
68 produced mainly by the liver. Once absorbed, iron is transported by transferrin, which delivers
69 iron to organs and cells by binding to transferrin receptors on cell membranes and transferring
70 iron into cells via DMT1 to a transient storage area called the labile iron pool, where it becomes
71 available for cellular functions. [\[1, 2, 3\]](#)

72 Excess iron is stored in ferritin, which serves as a reserve of iron.

73 Transferrin is variably saturated with iron (normal range: 30–45%). The saturation level of
74 transferrin regulates hepcidin production. Hepcidin also affects blood iron levels by
75 deactivating ferroportin, a protein that exports iron from cells, such as macrophages and
76 intestinal cells. When hepcidin binds to ferroportin, it induces its degradation, thereby
77 preventing iron from being exported from cells into the bloodstream. [\[1, 2, 3\]](#)

78 When blood iron levels drop, hepcidin production decreases. This allows ferroportin to release
79 stored iron from macrophages, and intestinal iron absorption increases to compensate for the
80 reduced blood iron levels. Consequently, serum iron and transferrin saturation can rise. [\[1, 2,](#)
81 [3\]](#)

82 When the body has sufficient or excess iron stores, hepcidin levels increase, causing the
83 degradation of ferroportin, which prevents the release of iron from cells. Intestinal iron
84 absorption is reduced, resulting in lower serum iron levels and transferrin saturation. This
85 regulation is crucial because excess iron is toxic and a source of oxidative stress. [\[1, 2, 3\]](#)

86

87 Hepcidin synthesis is increased by iron overload and decreased by anemia and hypoxia.
 88 Hepcidin is produced during inflammatory syndromes or infections, causing iron to be
 89 sequestered in macrophages and leading to a reduction in blood iron levels, which may result
 90 in anemia. [1, 2, 3]

91 Factors affecting iron metabolism

92 Primary Hemochromatosis: Genetic disorders of iron metabolism

93 Disturbances in the regulation of iron homeostasis can result in either iron deficiency, anemia,
 94 or iron overload, hemochromatosis. Various factors, including genetic causes, can influence
 95 iron accumulation in the body. [3]

96 Hereditary hemochromatosis is caused by genetic mutations leading to excessive iron
 97 absorption and retention. Several polymorphisms in various genes predispose to
 98 hemochromatosis; however, to date, four main types of genetic hemochromatosis have been
 99 identified. Among these, mutations in the HFE gene are most often associated with hereditary
 100 hemochromatosis, while rarer forms involve mutations in TFR2, HJV, HAMP, and SLC40A1. [4,
 101 5, 6]

102 Type 1 Hemochromatosis

103 Type 1 hemochromatosis is caused by mutations in the HFE gene, with the most common
 104 mutation being C282Y, and to a lesser extent H63D.

105 The C282Y mutation leads to reduced hepcidin production. With lower levels of hepcidin,
 106 ferroportin remains active, resulting in excessive iron absorption in the intestine and

107 uncontrolled release of stored iron from macrophages. Increased serum iron affects organs,
108 potentially causing liver diseases, cardiomyopathies, diabetes, and arthropathies. [7, 8, 9]

109 Type 2A and 2B Hemochromatosis

110 Type 2A Hemochromatosis results from mutations in the HJV gene. These mutations impair
111 BMP signaling, drastically reducing hepcidin production. This triggers massive iron absorption
112 from early childhood, leading to rapid and toxic accumulation in organs. Symptoms typically
113 appear during adolescence, and if left untreated, complications such as cirrhosis, early heart
114 failure, and severe endocrine disorders may arise. [7, 8, 9]

115 Type 2B Hemochromatosis involves mutations in the HAMP gene, which also reduce hepcidin
116 production and lead to rapid iron buildup in organs, causing severe symptoms from
117 adolescence onwards.

118 Type 3 Hemochromatosis

119 The TFR2 gene is implicated in type 3 hemochromatosis, a rarer form. Mutations in this gene
120 disrupt the transferrin receptor 2's ability to sense serum iron levels, resulting in reduced
121 hepcidin production. This leads to iron accumulation in organs, causing hepatic, cardiac, and
122 endocrine complications. [7, 8, 9]

123 Type 4A and 4B Hemochromatosis

124 Type 4 hemochromatosis, also known as ferroportin disease, directly affects ferroportin
125 function and is the most common form after type 1. It is caused by mutations in the SLC40A1
126 gene, which regulates iron export from cells into the bloodstream. [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]

127 Unlike other types of haemochromatosis, it is an autosomal dominant disease, with a single
128 mutation sufficient to trigger the disease. However, not all mutations are pathogenic.

129 Type 4A Hemochromatosis occurs due to loss-of-function mutations in ferroportin, preventing
130 iron export. Iron accumulates in intestinal cells, hepatocytes, and particularly macrophages.
131 This reduces iron availability for plasma and erythropoiesis, leading to moderate anemia.

132 Type 4B Hemochromatosis is caused by gain-of-function mutations in ferroportin, resulting in
133 increased iron export from macrophages into the bloodstream, resembling the presentation
134 of types 1-3 hemochromatosis.

135 Ferroportin disease can present as iron overload mainly in macrophages and the liver,
136 increasing the risk of cirrhosis and liver diseases. Unlike other forms of hemochromatosis, this
137 type does not always result in hyperferritinemia. Additionally, hereditary microcytic
138 hypochromic anemia is linked to ferroportin mutations preventing iron export from
139 macrophages.

140 Genetic mutations in the HFE, TFR2, HJV, HAMP, and SLC40A1 genes disrupt iron metabolism.
141 In types 1-3 and 4B hemochromatosis, reduced hepcidin production leads to increased
142 intestinal iron absorption. Most mutations cause hepcidin dysregulation, insufficient iron
143 retention in macrophages, organ accumulation, and clinical complications, which can become
144 severe if untreated.

145 Rare forms of genetic hemochromatosis exist

146 I will not review all the genes that influence iron metabolism, as they are numerous (a non-
147 exhaustive list can be found in the [appendix](#)). However, it could be worthwhile to deepen
148 research on genetic predisposition in patients with macrophagic myofasciitis, especially if no
149 specific polymorphisms for the most well-known forms of hemochromatosis would be found.

150 *BMP6*

151 The BMP6 gene regulates a wide range of biological processes, including the regulation of iron
152 metabolism. BMP6 is part of the TGF-beta (transforming growth factor-beta) superfamily of
153 proteins. It contributes to gene expression by influencing HAMP expression and acting as a
154 ligand for hemojuvelin (HJV), thereby affecting hepcidin levels. It also impacts the BMP-SMAD
155 signaling pathway in regulating iron metabolism. [[12](#), [13](#)]

156 Mutations in BMP6, including heterozygous mutations, have been associated with iron
157 overload.

158 *The N144H mutation*

159 We could mention the N144H mutation in the SLC11A3 gene, which codes for ferroportin. As
160 with SLC40A1, the N144H mutation is an autosomal dominant form of iron overload. [[14](#), [15](#)]

161

162 Other conditions affecting iron metabolism

163 Although MFM (macrophagic myofasciitis) patients do not typically present with other iron-
164 related disorders, it is nonetheless relevant to acknowledge their existence. Beyond
165 hereditary hemochromatosis, several physiological or pathological conditions can alter iron
166 distribution, particularly in macrophages. Given the rising prevalence of iron metabolism
167 disorders—whether of deficiency or overload—greater clinical attention is warranted.

168 **Conditions:**

- 169 • Inflammation
- 170 • Metabolic syndrome
- 171 • Infections
- 172 • Chronic hemolysis
- 173 • Myelodysplastic syndromes
- 174 • Stress
- 175 • Alcoholism
- 176 • Dopamine levels

177 Aside from mutations in genes involved in hereditary hemochromatosis, iron can be retained
178 in macrophages under several other pathological or physiological conditions.

179 **Chronic Inflammation**

180 Inflammation - particularly pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 - stimulates the production
181 of hepcidin by the liver. Hepcidin degrades ferroportin, causing iron retention in macrophages

182 and leading to anemia. Anemia associated with chronic diseases is not indicative of iron stores,
183 as inflammation prevents iron release. Serum iron levels are low despite sufficient iron stores.
184 This inflammatory anemia reduces the iron available for erythropoiesis. [16, 17]

185 Independently of hepcidin, pro-inflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha
186 (TNF- α) and interleukin-1 (IL-1) also inhibit ferroportin expression.

187 When macrophages accumulate excessive iron in response to chronic inflammation, oxidative
188 stress increases, further exacerbating the inflammatory process. [18]

189 Infections

190 To deprive pathogenic microorganisms of iron and inhibit their growth, infections can lead to
191 iron sequestration in macrophages. Like inflammation, this condition can result in anemia. [19]

192 Liver Diseases

193 Thirty percent of patients with end-stage liver disease exhibit iron overload. [20]

194 Metabolic syndrome

195 Metabolic syndrome, which is associated with type 2 diabetes, hypertension, nonalcoholic
196 fatty liver disease (NAFLD), and polycystic ovarian syndrome (POS), is often accompanied by
197 elevated ferritin. [21, 22, 23]

198 Chronic Hemolysis

199 Premature destruction of red blood cells, known as chronic hemolysis, leads to iron
200 accumulation in macrophages. [24]

201 Myelodysplastic Syndromes

202 Myelodysplastic syndromes result in ineffective erythropoiesis, causing increased iron
203 absorption by macrophages and iron overload. Anemia may also occur consequently. [25]

204 Iron Overload from Repeated Transfusions

205 In conditions requiring repeated blood transfusions, such as major thalassemia, iron overload
206 can develop in macrophages. [26]

207 Hypoxia

208 Hypoxia stimulates hepcidin production, increasing iron and aluminum retention in cells,
209 particularly in macrophages. Aluminum itself can induce hypoxia. [27]

210 Alcoholism

211 Alcohol consumption is associated with a higher risk of iron overload, particularly in the liver
212 and brain. Alcohol reduces hepcidin expression in the liver by inducing oxidative stress. [28,
213 29]

214 Stress and Dopamine Levels

215 Stress and elevated dopamine levels influence iron metabolism by increasing iron uptake and
216 storage in macrophages, partly due to dopamine's role in regulating divalent metal

217 transporter 1 (DMT1) activity. This connection may be relevant to neuroinflammatory
218 conditions. [[30](#), [31](#)]

219 Several of these mechanisms—particularly inflammation, hypoxia, and altered hepcidin
220 levels—not only affect iron homeostasis but may also influence the biodistribution and
221 retention of other metals, such as aluminum. These complex interactions underline the
222 importance of a thorough diagnostic approach when investigating metal accumulation.

223

224 Diagnostic Methods

225 Iron Panel

226 An iron panel evaluates the body's iron status using several key markers. This comprehensive
227 assessment is not routinely performed; only ferritin levels are sometimes measured.

228 *Serum Iron:* This measures the amount of circulating iron in the blood, most of which is bound
229 to transferrin. In cases of iron deficiency, there is insufficient iron available for recycling,
230 leading to lower circulating iron levels. In inflammatory anemia, increased hepcidin levels trap
231 iron in macrophages, reducing the iron available in the bloodstream. [[32](#)]

232 *Ferritin:* Ferritin is the primary protein responsible for storing iron in the body. Reference
233 ranges vary by age, sex, and testing method. Normal ferritin levels range from 30 to 300 µg/L
234 in men and 15 to 200 µg/L in women. Ferritin levels increase in inflammatory states due to
235 ferritin secretion by macrophages that retain iron. [[33](#), [34](#)]

236 *Total Iron-Binding Capacity (TIBC):* This measures transferrin's capacity to bind iron. It is
237 calculated using serum iron and unsaturated iron-binding capacity (UIBC). TIBC is elevated
238 when the body is iron-deficient because more binding sites are available to absorb iron. In
239 contrast, TIBC is lower when transferrin levels are reduced.

240 *Transferrin Production:* Transferrin levels vary depending on iron stores in the body. When iron
241 reserves are low, transferrin levels increase to enhance iron absorption and transport. In
242 inflammatory states, cytokines reduce transferrin production, leading to lower levels.

243 *Transferrin Saturation:* This is the most sensitive marker for detecting iron overload, as it is
244 elevated in hereditary hemochromatosis. Transferrin saturation represents the ratio of serum
245 iron to TIBC. This percentage decreases in both iron deficiency and inflammatory anemia. [[35](#),
246 [36](#)]

247

Serum iron	It circulates in the blood It is low in cases of iron deficiency and inflammatory anemia
Ferritin	Storage protein that is often elevated in genetic hemochromatosis or inflammatory anemia. Elevated ferritin can also be associated with liver damage.

Transferrin	Transport protein whose level increases in cases of iron deficiency. Inflammation reduces its production
Transferrin binding capacity	Total iron binding capacity is the amount of available iron binding sites on transferrin.
Transferrin saturation coefficient	Transferrin saturation is calculated by dividing serum iron by the binding capacity. This indicator is often elevated in patients with hemochromatosis.

248

249 **Table of results of iron panel in different pathological conditions**

250 [[37](#), [38](#), [39](#), [40](#)]

CONDITION	Mean glomerular volume	Serum iron	Ferritin	Total iron-binding capacity (TIBC)	Transferrin	Transferrin saturation	Liver Enzymes (ALT/AST/GGT)
Iron deficiency	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	Usually normal
Inflammatory anemia	→	↓	↑	↓	↓	↓	Usually normal or mildly elevated if comorbidity (e.g., autoimmune hepatitis)
Minor thalassemia	↓	→	→	→	→	→	Frequently elevated
Major thalassemia	↓	→ ↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	Frequently elevated
Sideroblastic anemia	↓	↑	↑	→	→ ↑	↑	Depending on underlying causes
Iron overload, Hemochromatosis	→	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	Often elevated (especially ALT and AST in early stages; GGT may increase in later fibrosis)
Macrophagic myofasciitis		→ ↓	↓	Could be low	↓	Could be low	Possibly normal or mildly elevated (based on anecdotal reports)

251

252 These values are indicative and may vary depending on the clinical situation. Each case is unique, and
253 only a personalized medical analysis can provide tailored recommendations.

254

255 Genetic Testing

256 Genetic testing is performed only when genetic hemochromatosis is suspected. The most
257 frequently analyzed mutation is C282Y on the HFE gene. If metabolic and immune causes are
258 ruled out and the C282Y mutation is absent, other forms of genetic hemochromatosis are
259 explored by specialized reference centers. [\[41\]](#)

260 Liver Examinations

261 To evaluate the impact of iron overload on the liver and identify potential complications, such
262 as fibrosis or cirrhosis, several tests may be performed.

263 The main tests include:

264 *Liver Panel:*

265 Transaminases (ALT, AST): Elevated levels indicate liver damage due to iron overload. [\[41\]](#)

266 Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT): Often elevated in liver dysfunction.

267 Alkaline phosphatase (ALP): Used to detect liver or bile duct issues.

268 Bilirubin: High levels may indicate advanced liver dysfunction. [\[42\]](#)

269 *Hepatic MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging):*

270 Provides a non-invasive assessment of liver iron content and detects fibrosis or cirrhosis
271 without requiring a biopsy. [\[43, 44, 45\]](#)

272 *FibroScan:*

273 Measures liver elasticity to evaluate fibrosis. Often used to detect liver damage in
274 hemochromatosis patients. [\[46\]](#)

275 *Liver Biopsy:*

276 Conducted in cases of uncertainty regarding the severity of liver damage. It measures iron
277 levels in liver tissue and determines the stage of fibrosis or cirrhosis. [\[47\]](#)

278 Aluminum and Competition with Iron in Metabolism

279 Iron Metabolism Influences the Metabolism of Other Metals

280 Iron metabolism is closely linked to the regulation of other essential metals and minerals such
281 as magnesium, calcium, zinc, copper, as well as toxic metals like mercury, lead, cadmium, and
282 aluminum. Proteins involved in iron transport and regulation - such as transferrin, Divalent
283 Metal Transporter 1 (DMT1), and ferroportin - often play pivotal roles in managing these other
284 metals. [\[48\]](#)

285 When addressing an iron deficiency, the body increases its absorption capacity for iron,
286 inadvertently enhancing the absorption of toxic metals like mercury, lead, cadmium, and
287 aluminum. [\[48\]](#)

288 Iron deficiency may result in increased levels of zinc, copper, and manganese in the brain,
289 potentially impairing neurological function and exacerbating neurodegenerative disorders.
290 Conversely, elevated zinc and cobalt levels are frequently observed in individuals with iron
291 overload. [48]

292 Animal studies reveal that manganese metabolism closely mirrors that of iron. Iron deficiency
293 stimulates manganese absorption, while iron overload may decrease it, highlighting a
294 regulatory interplay between the two metals. [48]

295 In genetic hemochromatosis, high levels of zinc are observed in the liver, although plasma zinc
296 levels remain normal. In cases of cirrhosis with iron overload, intestinal absorption of cobalt is
297 increased, underscoring the interconnection between these metals in the liver. [48]

298 Calcium plays a vital role as a cofactor for ferroportin, the key protein responsible for exporting
299 iron from cells into the bloodstream. Physiological plasma calcium levels enhance iron
300 transport by ferroportin. Additionally, extracellular calcium influences the efflux of other
301 metals like cobalt and zinc, demonstrating calcium's critical role in regulating metal transport.
302 [49]

303 Disruptions in proteins involved in iron metabolism can have cascading effects on the
304 metabolism of other metals.

305

306 Lead Accumulation and Iron-Related Genetic Polymorphisms

307 Several studies have explored the interaction between genetic variants involved in iron
308 metabolism and susceptibility to lead (Pb) toxicity. Evidence suggests that individuals
309 carrying polymorphisms in genes such as *HFE* (H63D and C282Y) and *TF* (P570S) exhibit
310 significantly higher blood lead levels. In a cohort of 422 Mexican children, carriers of *HFE* or
311 *TF* variants had 11% and 10% higher blood lead concentrations, respectively, compared to
312 wild-type individuals. Notably, those carrying both variants had blood lead levels 50% higher
313 than wild types, suggesting a strong gene–environment interaction. [50] [51] [52]

314 Further research has confirmed that these polymorphisms may enhance lead absorption and
315 retention, thereby increasing individual vulnerability to metal-induced toxicity. Furthermore,
316 gene–environment interaction studies have linked lead burden and oxidative stress
317 biomarkers to variations in iron-handling genes. [53] [54] [55]

318 This crosstalk between iron metabolism and the biotransformation of toxic metals like lead
319 highlights a broader paradigm in which genetic and metabolic factors can amplify vulnerability
320 to metal-induced toxicity. Aluminum, another pervasive environmental metal, also interferes
321 with iron pathways—often with inflammatory and neurotoxic consequences.

322

323 Aluminum Disrupts Iron Metabolism

324 The ionic form of aluminum (Al^{3+}) - the one present in vaccines - and iron, use similar
325 mechanisms of transport and absorption in the body, notably via transferrin. Aluminum is also
326 stored in ferritin, an iron storage protein in cells such as macrophages. [56, 57, 58]

327 Aluminum competes with iron and causes iron deficiency in macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF).
328 Iron deficiency exacerbates the toxic effects of aluminum by disrupting multiple biological
329 processes that require iron, including cellular respiration, hemoglobin production, oxygen
330 transport, and others. Aluminum-induced metabolic disturbances are one reason for the
331 multisystemic reactions observed in MMF, as iron is a cofactor for numerous enzymes like
332 catalase and cytochromes. [59]

333 By binding to transferrin, aluminum negatively regulates the expression of transferrin
334 receptors, such as TFR2. In vitro and in vivo animal studies have shown that aluminum
335 accumulation causes anemia and reduces cellular iron uptake. [60]

336 In dialysis patients, aluminum levels inversely correlate with serum iron levels, ferritin, and
337 transferrin saturation. Iron deficiency increases aluminum uptake in cells, which can
338 perpetuate and even worsen anemia. Notably, low serum aluminum levels may coexist with
339 bone aluminum overload, leading to bone diseases. [61, 62, 63, 64]

340 Other animal studies suggest that increased aluminum in tissues is associated with higher iron
341 content in the brain, kidneys, liver, heart, and spleen. Aluminum stimulates the uptake of
342 transferrin-bound iron and free iron in glial cells, promoting oxidative stress. [65,66]

343 A 2001 study on 16 MMF patients found that all of them suffered from restless legs syndrome
344 (RLS), which has been attributed by many studies to iron deficiency, particularly in the brain.
345 RLS is also common in multiple sclerosis patients. [67, 68, 69, 70] However, genetic mutations
346 that increase iron accumulation do not seem to protect against RLS. [71] Conversely, hypoxia -
347 one potential cause being aluminum toxicity - has been shown to aggravate RLS. [72]

348 Dopamine, which increases iron retention in macrophages and neurons, explains the efficacy
349 of dopamine agonists in treating RLS and Parkinson's disease. [73]

350

351 Macrophages in Iron and Aluminum Metabolism

352 Macrophages are immune cells that play a vital role in combating infections by restricting
353 pathogen access to iron. They are integral to iron metabolism, particularly hepatic and
354 splenic macrophages, which phagocytize senescent erythrocytes to recycle iron. [74]

355 When macrophages encounter aluminum, phagocytosis is activated. Aluminum exposure
356 also triggers autophagy and an inflammatory response characterized by early production of
357 $\text{TNF-}\alpha$ and IL-6. This process disrupts mitochondrial metabolism, reducing oxygen
358 consumption and leading to hypoxia. IL-6, in turn, influences iron metabolism and is
359 implicated in inflammatory anemia. [75]

360 Interactions Between Iron and Aluminum: Autophagy, 361 Ferroptosis, and Genetic Perspectives

362

363 Autophagy, Ferroptosis, and Their Interactions

364 Autophagy is a cellular cleanup mechanism that removes damaged proteins, organelles,
365 intracellular pathogens, and toxic metabolites to maintain cellular homeostasis. Dysfunctions
366 in autophagy are observed in several diseases, including neurodegenerative diseases, cancer,
367 and diabetes. This process helps the body produce energy and sustain vital cellular functions
368 under severe stress, such as nutrient deprivation. By preventing programmed cell death
369 (apoptosis), autophagy supports cell survival. [[76](#), [77](#), [78](#), [79](#)]

370 Polymorphisms in genes involved in autophagy could impair the cells' ability to eliminate
371 aluminum effectively, leading to chronic inflammatory responses. These genetic variations may
372 render some individuals more vulnerable to aluminum's harmful effects. [[80](#)]

373 Ferroptosis, on the other hand, is a form of cell death tied to disruptions in iron and lipid
374 metabolism. It occurs when the cell's antioxidant system is overwhelmed, particularly under
375 exposure to toxic compounds. In cases of iron overload, free iron (Fe^{2+}) boosts the production
376 of free radicals via the Fenton reaction, leading to lipid peroxidation of cell membranes. [[81](#),
377 [82](#)]

378 Autophagy can release iron through a process called ferritinophagy, which degrades
379 mitochondria and lysosomes, contributing to excess free iron and promoting ferroptosis. This
380 exacerbates oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation. Conversely, autophagy can protect against
381 ferroptosis by clearing damaged organelles, like defective mitochondria (via mitophagy),
382 reducing free radical production. [[83](#), [84](#), [85](#)]

383

384 Potential Mechanisms in MMF

385 Interactions between autophagy and ferroptosis might play a crucial role in macrophagic
386 myofasciitis (MMF). Possible key mechanisms include:

387 **Iron-Aluminum Competition:** Competition between aluminum and iron for transport and
388 storage increases free iron levels, amplifying oxidative stress. [[86](#)]

389 **Gene Polymorphisms:** Mutations in genes associated with iron metabolism and autophagy
390 may interact, compounding dysfunctions. [[86](#)]

391 **Inflammation and Immunity:** Aluminum promotes inflammation and disrupts immune
392 function, destabilizing lysosomes and impairing autophagic activity. Elevated free iron levels
393 due to aluminum presence may also trigger ferroptosis. [[87](#), [88](#)]

394 In MMF patients, cellular differences compared to controls include the expression of Rubicon,
395 a molecule linked to reduced autophagic activity, following vaccine administration. Similarly,

396 iron overload inhibits lysosomal regeneration, leading to autophagosomes' accumulation in
397 microglia, significantly impairing autophagy and enhancing ferroptosis. Dysregulated
398 autophagy in microglia is associated with neurodegenerative diseases, and patients with
399 hemochromatosis may struggle more to clear vaccine-related aluminum due to pre-existing
400 autophagy deficits. [89, 90, 91, 92]

401 Finally, iron is critical for regulating autophagy, meaning both iron overload and deficiency can
402 lead to autophagic dysfunction. This underscores the crucial role of iron metabolism in
403 maintaining proper autophagic processes. [93, 94]

404

405 The impact of genetic hemochromatosis on aluminum 406 metabolism

407 Mutations in genes involved in type 1, 2, 3, and 4b hemochromatosis affect the regulation of
408 hepcidin, leading to an overload of serum iron, ferritin, and transferrin saturation. This
409 overload may influence the metabolism of other metals, including aluminum, which shares
410 some absorption, transport, and storage mechanisms with iron.

411 Aluminum and iron are transported via transferrin. The level of transferrin saturation with iron
412 impacts aluminum binding to this protein. [95]

413 If a person already has transferrin excessively saturated with iron (an early sign of
414 hemochromatosis), this could affect aluminum transport and clearance. An oversaturation of
415 transferrin might increase the retention of aluminum injected into macrophages. Aluminum
416 also competes with iron for storage mechanisms, notably in ferritin. Iron overload could
417 increase the proportion of unbound aluminum, raising its toxicity.

418 During iron overload, hepcidin levels rise and degrade ferroportin, preventing the release of
419 iron from macrophages. This can be accompanied by anemia. [4]

420 Aluminum-containing vaccinations are introduced early in life. The injection of aluminum at a
421 young age could interfere with the underlying mechanisms of genetic hemochromatosis.
422 Successive vaccinations causing acute aluminum exposure could lead to early-onset
423 aluminum-related hemochromatosis that might go undetected. In France, half of the
424 aluminum vaccine exposure occurs within the first year of life. [96, 97, 98]

425 While genetic hemochromatosis predisposes individuals to increased absorption of ingested
426 iron and aluminum, it is important to note that the usual absorption rate for ingested
427 aluminum is less than 1%, whereas absorption from intramuscular vaccine injections
428 approaches 100%. [99, 100]

429 In macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF), aluminum is found embedded in macrophages. The
430 function of these immune cells is influenced by iron metabolism, which is why genetic
431 polymorphisms might lead to the retention of vaccine-derived aluminum. Genetic
432 dysregulation of iron metabolism could result in prolonged retention of aluminum in

433 macrophages at the injection site, exacerbating local and systemic effects. The occurrence of
434 familial cases of MMF has long suggested a genetic predisposition. [[101](#), [102](#), [103](#), [104](#)]

435 All forms of genetic hemochromatosis are likely to influence the clearance and tolerance of
436 aluminum injected via vaccines. The first three forms of hemochromatosis and type 4b are
437 particularly associated with iron overload in organs such as the liver, heart, pancreas, and
438 brain. Mutations in the HFE, HAMP, HJV, and TFR2 genes reduce hepcidin production,
439 activating ferroportin and thereby increasing iron absorption and its release from
440 macrophages, contributing to iron overload in plasma and organs. Disruptions in iron transport
441 mechanisms might contribute to aluminum retention. [[105](#)]

442 Iron retention in macrophages is primarily associated with type 4a hemochromatosis. Certain
443 mutations in the SLC40A1 gene, which encodes ferroportin, may disrupt, not only iron
444 metabolism but also that of other metals such as zinc or calcium. Individuals with genetic
445 polymorphisms in the SLC40A1 gene may specifically retain aluminum in their macrophages,
446 as observed in biopsy samples from vaccine injection sites in individuals with MMF. [[106](#)]

447 Polymorphisms in the SLC40A1 gene lead to intracellular iron overload, inducing ferroptosis.
448 [[107](#)]

449 Sixty-five mutations have already been identified, with new ones being added regularly. [[108](#),
450 [109](#), [110](#), [111](#)]

451 However, interactions between mutations in genes involved in autophagy and those in iron
452 metabolism could exist in MMF. The SLC40A1 gene is not only involved in iron metabolism but
453 it is also linked to immunity and autophagy. Some mutations in SLC40A1 result in a gain of
454 function, while others cause a loss of function. The expression of the SLC40A1 gene regulates
455 autophagy, with a gain of function promoting autophagosome formation. Overexpression of
456 SLC40A1 suppresses invasion and metastasis of liver cancer cells. Conversely, loss of function
457 of this gene leads to reduced autophagy. [[112](#), [113](#)]

458 Underexpression of the SLC40A1 gene causes iron retention in macrophages, which may be
459 accompanied by anemia. Diagnosing this type of hemochromatosis is challenging because
460 typical markers such as ferritin or transferrin saturation may remain low or normal. It is
461 therefore possible to suffer from iron overload and anemia simultaneously. Genetic
462 polymorphisms in the SLC40A1 gene could cause aluminum retention in macrophages. [[10](#)]

463

464 Iron and aluminum accumulation and inflammatory 465 pathologies: Focus on macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF)

466 MMF, inflammatory disease

467 Macrophagic Myofasciitis (MMF) was discovered in the late 1990s and is associated with the
468 persistent presence of aluminum adjuvants used in certain vaccines to enhance the immune
469 response at the injection site. [[114](#)]

470 In MMF, aluminum injected into the muscle is not properly eliminated by the body but is
471 instead captured within macrophages, forming persistent deposits at the injection site. Studies
472 in animals have shown that aluminum adjuvants can travel to distant organs, including the
473 brain, with low-dose neurotoxic and inflammatory effects. These aluminum deposits in
474 macrophages are visible in muscle biopsies taken from the deltoid and trigger long-term
475 systemic immune stimulation. [[115](#), [116](#), [117](#)]

476 MMF is a rare and highly debilitating disease, and its true prevalence is likely underestimated
477 due to a lack of awareness. Patients are often misdiagnosed because their symptoms can
478 mimic those of other conditions, such as chronic fatigue syndrome or fibromyalgia.

479 Patients with MMF experience severe systemic and neurological symptoms, including:

- 480 • Persistent physical and cognitive exhaustion not relieved by rest.
- 481 • Generalized myalgia and arthralgia, often highly disabling.
- 482 • Cognitive impairments: difficulties with concentration, short-term memory loss, "brain
483 fog."
- 484 • Sleep disturbances: insomnia, non-restorative sleep.
- 485 • Peripheral neurological symptoms: paresthesia (tingling, numbness), and sometimes
486 muscle weakness.
- 487 • Digestive issues.

488 Vaccines implicated include those for hepatitis B or A, DTP, papillomavirus, and others. Genetic
489 predisposition factors are being explored by research teams, as MMF patients may have
490 difficulties eliminating aluminum. Genetic polymorphisms affecting the autophagy system are
491 still under investigation.

492 Mutations in genes involved in iron metabolism, such as SLC40A1, TFR2, and HFE, or others
493 affecting hepcidin regulation, may influence aluminum retention. The retention of aluminum
494 in macrophages could be exacerbated by genetic mutations.

495 Aluminum interacts with iron metabolism as it utilizes similar pathways for absorption,
496 transport, and storage. MMF patients typically present with iron deficiency.

497 Diagnosing MMF is complex and involves multiple elements:

- 498 • Clinical presentation.
- 499 • Muscle biopsy from the deltoid: aluminum infiltration in macrophages.
- 500 • PET scan.
- 501 • Neuropsychological tests.

502

503 Iron and aluminum are implicated in other inflammatory diseases

504 The clinical manifestations of hemochromatosis are numerous: [[118](#)]

- 505 • Unexplained weakness or fatigue
- 506 • Abdominal pain

- 507 • Joint pain, arthritis
- 508 • Liver disorders
- 509 • Type 2 diabetes
- 510 • Irregular heartbeat
- 511 • Reduced libido, impotence
- 512 • Osteoporosis
- 513 • Skin discoloration or bronzing
- 514 • Mood swings and irritability

515 Iron is a crucial element for brain development, neurotransmitter synthesis, neuronal
516 functioning, and mitochondrial activity. Therefore, disturbances in iron metabolism, whether
517 deficiency or overload, are observed in various diseases, particularly neurodegenerative ones.
518 Iron accumulation in the brain triggers neurological and psychiatric disorders. [[119](#)]

519 Iron accumulation in the brain is linked to Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases. [[120](#)]

520 Animal studies have shown that iron overload in the substantia nigra causes low dopamine
521 levels and damage to dopaminergic neurons, as seen in Parkinson's disease. Links between
522 mutations in genes involved in iron metabolism, such as transferrin receptor 2 (TFR2) and
523 transferrin (TF), and Parkinson's disease have been observed. [[121](#)]

524 Ferroptosis is involved in neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's, Alzheimer's,
525 Huntington's disease, multiple sclerosis, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. [[122](#)]

526 High iron levels have been observed in the white and gray matter of patients with multiple
527 sclerosis, as well as in the macrophages of the basal ganglia. [[123](#)]

528 Elevated ferritin levels have been noted in patients with bipolar disorder. Ferritin could be a
529 marker of oxidative stress and low-grade inflammation present in this pathology. [[124](#)]

530 The analysis of the prefrontal cortex of individuals with schizophrenia has also shown
531 disruptions in iron metabolism, with reduced ferritin and increased free iron. [[125](#)]

532 The risks of psychiatric disorders increase with iron deficiency. [[126](#)]

533 Dysfunctions in ferroptosis and increased oxidative stress are present in type 2 diabetes. Iron
534 overload is associated with insulin resistance and elevated triglycerides. [[127](#), [128](#)]

535 Underexpression of the SLC40A1 gene and intracellular iron accumulation cause cancer cell
536 proliferation in multiple myeloma. [[129](#)]

537 A study by Rabaya et al. analyzed several genes involved in iron metabolism (TFRC, SLC11A2,
538 SLC40A1, HAMP) in 48 autistic individuals compared to 88 controls and found significant
539 differences between the two groups, particularly in genes rs11915082 (TFRC) and rs1439816
540 (SLC40A1). [[130](#)]

541 Transferrin levels are associated with an increased risk of autism. Some studies have observed
542 higher transferrin levels, while lower levels of transferrin and ceruloplasmin (a copper-binding
543 protein) have been associated with language loss in autistic children. [[131](#), [132](#)]

544 Transferrin and ceruloplasmin are antioxidant proteins, and their low levels have been linked
545 to higher lipid peroxidation in autistic children. Mutations in the transferrin (TF) genes have
546 been associated with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) in children from Bangladesh. [\[133,134\]](#)

547 Genetic polymorphisms involved in serum transferrin levels are significantly associated with
548 an increased risk of autism. [\[135\]](#)

549 Ireland, particularly Northern Ireland, has the highest prevalence of autism in Europe and one
550 of the highest globally. One in 20 children in Northern Ireland has been diagnosed with autism
551 spectrum disorders. Many adults remain undiagnosed. [\[136\]](#) Ireland also has the highest
552 prevalence of hemochromatosis worldwide. While correlation does not imply causation, it may
553 not be a coincidence. [\[137\]](#)

554 Aluminum has also been implicated in several inflammatory, neurodegenerative, or
555 autoimmune disorders. [\[138, 139\]](#)

556 Mitochondrial dysfunction is associated with many pathologies, and iron or aluminum
557 accumulation can disrupt cellular respiration, energy production, and increase reactive oxygen
558 species. [\[140\]](#)

559 Brain tissue analyses of individuals with Alzheimer's, autism, or multiple sclerosis have shown
560 significantly higher aluminum content than in the brains of people without these conditions.
561 [\[141\]](#)

562 Several studies suggest that aluminum adjuvants may contribute to the increase in autism
563 spectrum disorders. [\[142\]](#)

564 Compared to controls, high aluminum levels have been observed in the ferritin of individuals
565 with Alzheimer's disease. High levels of iron and aluminum are also present in the nuclei of
566 nerve cells in patients. [\[143, 144\]](#)

567 Aluminum-induced iron deficiency impairs mitochondrial function. [\[145, 146\]](#)

568 Animal studies show that defects in autophagy cause neurological developmental disruptions
569 and behavioral disorders. [\[147\]](#)

570 Genes associated with brain disorders such as autism spectrum disorders are particularly
571 present in autophagy pathways. [\[148\]](#)

572 Alterations in synaptic development linked to autophagy are observed in autism spectrum
573 disorders. Autism, where disruptions in the immune system and autophagy are noted, is the
574 subject of clinical and experimental research to explore the role of aluminum adjuvants in the
575 onset of autism spectrum disorders (ASD). [\[149, 150\]](#)

576

577 Prenatal Stress, Ferroportin, and Metal Susceptibility: A Critical 578 Window

579 Recent findings indicate that prenatal stress can modulate iron regulation very early in
580 development, particularly through cholinergic signaling and fetal macrophages. Stress
581 activates the cholinergic system via $\alpha 7$ nicotinic receptors, which—beyond their anti-
582 inflammatory role—interact with the ferroportin pathway, the key protein responsible for
583 exporting iron from cells. This interference may lead to increased intracellular iron retention,
584 especially in immune cells, thereby altering iron homeostasis. [[151](#), [152](#)]

585 These changes may represent adaptive responses aimed at limiting oxidative stress and
586 infection by reducing circulating free iron. However, they could also predispose to increased
587 accumulation of toxic metals such as aluminum, which share similar cellular pathways for
588 transport and storage. [[153](#)]

589 This link between early stress, ferroportin, and iron metabolism disruption is particularly
590 concerning, as it could affect a large number of individuals exposed in utero to maternal stress
591 or inflammation. Genetic variations affecting ferroportin or transferrin have indeed been
592 identified in neurodevelopmental disorders such as autism, suggesting a gene–environment
593 interaction that promotes early-life metal dysregulation. [[154](#), [155](#), [156](#), [157](#)]

594 Ferroportin, already suspected in this article to play a key role in aluminum accumulation
595 within macrophages in MMF, may thus lie at the core of broader mechanisms linking prenatal
596 stress, inflammation, and metal toxicity.

597 Clinical and therapeutic implications: management of 598 genetically predisposed patients

599 Management of hemochromatosis

600 The average time to diagnosis for hemochromatosis is estimated to be between 10 and 15
601 years after the onset of the first symptoms. Symptoms appear once iron accumulation
602 becomes significant and often remain general and nonspecific (fatigue, joint pain, abdominal
603 pain) until an advanced stage when liver and cardiac damage occur. Yet, early diagnosis is
604 crucial to preventing complications, and treatment is effective and low-cost. [[158](#), [159](#)]

605 About half of individuals with the homozygous C282Y mutation do not show symptoms of iron
606 overload. Conversely, some individuals with heterozygous mutations develop iron overload.
607 Gene-environment interactions may influence the phenotype, and other non-HFE genes could
608 be involved in the disease. Various combinations of deleterious variants - not necessarily
609 homozygous - might affect iron accumulation. [[160](#), [48](#)]

610 There is no physiological pathway for excreting iron from the body, as it is constantly recycled.
611 The best method to reduce iron levels is through phlebotomies, which eliminate iron from
612 organs like the liver. With reduced circulating iron, the body uses its reserves to produce red

613 blood cells. Plasma donation has shown greater efficacy in reducing iron overload, but this
614 treatment is less widely applicable due to stricter requirements, such as vein size. [\[161\]](#)

615 Type 4a hemochromatosis is often accompanied by moderate anemia, making phlebotomies
616 challenging. However, a study demonstrated that long-term phlebotomy therapy reduced
617 hepatic iron in a patient with the H507R mutation in the SLC40A1 gene. [\[162\]](#)

618 For ferroportin disease type A, non-aggressive phlebotomies are recommended to improve
619 tolerance and avoid iron deficiency anemia. As with other types of hemochromatosis, genetic
620 screening is mandatory for descendants. [\[163\]](#)

621 However, phlebotomies performed for hemochromatosis do not resolve all symptoms, such as
622 osteoporosis, which can persist.

623 Iron chelation therapy is sometimes used when phlebotomies are not recommended, for
624 instance, when anemia is a concern. Various chelators, such as deferasirox, deferoxamine, or
625 deferiprone, are available. These agents may have beneficial effects on autophagy and
626 ferroptosis, though their administration often causes significant side effects. [\[164\]](#)

627 Rapamycin, an autophagy inducer, has shown benefits in animal studies of autism spectrum
628 disorders. However, the use of rapamycin might be useful only in a pre-disease period. [\[165,](#)
629 [166\]](#)

630

631 **Treatments and management of MMF**

632 The average delay between the onset of the clinical phase of MMF (Macrophagic Myofasciitis)
633 and biopsy is 67 months. The relatively rapid onset of MMF after vaccination (average of 11
634 months) might be attributed to genetic differences in iron metabolism. [\[74, 167\]](#)

635 MMF has no curative treatment; alleviating symptoms and maintaining an acceptable quality
636 of life remain the primary goals. Could the standard treatment for hemochromatosis -
637 phlebotomies - also benefit MMF patients? Since these patients often suffer from aluminum-
638 induced iron deficiency, phlebotomy might pose a risk to the body.

639 A management approach like that used in ferroportin disease, involving gentle phlebotomies
640 and close monitoring of iron levels, might be worth exploring. Could this reduce certain
641 symptoms and improve the quality of life for these patients? Currently, no studies have
642 demonstrated this. While the reduction of iron in peripheral tissues such as the liver or heart
643 through phlebotomies is well-documented, it is unknown whether the same effect applies to
644 the brain. [\[168\]](#)

645 The brain contains ferroportin, suggesting that iron can be exported from brain cells. Animal
646 studies and research on Alzheimer's patients have shown that ferroportin is downregulated,
647 leading to increased ferroptosis. Exported iron does indeed return to the bloodstream;
648 however, because it is continuously recycled and relies on functional ferroportin for export,
649 this mechanism is impaired in hemochromatosis and possibly also in MMF patients. [\[169\]](#)

650 Unfortunately, aluminum accumulated in the brains of MMF patients may never be expelled.
651 The use of iron chelators in neurodegeneration with brain iron accumulation (NBIA), a rare
652 hereditary neurological disorder, has not yielded positive effects. [[170](#), [171](#), [172](#)]

653 Since current treatments offer neither guaranteed efficacy nor safety, prevention would be
654 preferable to attempting a cure.

655

656 Prevention

657 Research into hemochromatosis and aluminum

658 Based on the interactions between iron and aluminum metabolism, individuals with primary
659 or even “secondary hemochromatosis” should be considered at risk of retaining vaccine-
660 derived aluminum rather than eliminating it, and preventive measures should be implemented
661 accordingly.

662 It is challenging to determine the exact prevalence of genetic hemochromatosis. The
663 homozygous Cys282Tyr mutation in the HFE gene is found in approximately 0.4% of
664 Caucasians, making hemochromatosis the most common genetic disorder. The heterozygous
665 C282Y variant is present in 1 in 10 individuals in Northern Europe. [[173](#)]

666 This condition is far more prevalent among Celtic populations, with a prevalence of 1 in 200
667 among Bretons and a predisposition rate of 1 in 83 in Ireland, where it is the most widespread
668 globally. For this reason, hemochromatosis is referred to as the “Celtic curse.” [[174](#), [175](#)]

669 A study published in BMJ Open analyzed data from 450,000 participants of European descent
670 from the UK Biobank over 13 years. It estimated that only 12% of men and 3.4% of women
671 with the homozygous C282Y variant were diagnosed. However, these variants increase the risk
672 of iron overload in the liver. By the end of the study period, 22% of men and 10% of women
673 with the variant had developed iron overload. [[176](#)]

674 Non-HFE hemochromatosis forms are less prevalent in Northern Europe, and the C282Y
675 mutation is less common elsewhere globally, where other hemochromatosis forms represent
676 a larger proportion. Studies suggest that recessively inherited non-HFE hemochromatosis
677 forms are rare, but population sample sizes may be too small to accurately evaluate these rare
678 metabolic issues. Therefore, the prevalence could be higher. [[177](#)]

679 Pathogenic mutations in the SLC40A1 gene, an autosomal dominant disorder, are relatively
680 frequent globally: 0.25% among Africans, 0.039% among Americans, and 0.033% among East
681 Asians. [[177](#)]

682 Due to the competition between aluminum and iron for transport proteins such as transferrin,
683 screening for common and less common mutations in genes involved in iron regulation (HFE,
684 TFR2, and SLC40A1) should be promptly considered to determine whether a specific genetic
685 pattern is associated with MMF. If confirmed, therapeutic approaches targeting iron regulation
686 could be evaluated.

687 If MMF patients have a genetic predisposition to hemochromatosis (HFE or non-HFE), an initial
688 prevention step would involve direct and indirect descendants undergoing genetic testing
689 before any vaccination with aluminum-containing adjuvants. Safer alternatives should be
690 offered. Calcium phosphate-adjuvanted vaccines, recognized as effective and long advocated
691 by E3M (the French association for macrophagic myofasciitis patients), should be made
692 available to avoid unnecessary risks. [\[178\]](#)

693 Given that hemochromatosis is the most widespread genetic disorder, extending pre-
694 vaccination tests to the general population could reduce disease risks and alleviate the
695 economic burden of severe illnesses, whose prevalence continues to rise.

696 Iron deficiency or overload can increase susceptibility to heavy metal toxicity, particularly
697 aluminum. This highlights the need to monitor iron status, especially in populations at risk of
698 iron overload or deficiency, to prevent toxic accumulation of other metals.

699 Some researchers advocate screening for iron overload (ferritin and transferrin saturation
700 levels) and generalized genetic testing within the population to identify individuals at genetic
701 risk of hemochromatosis and prevent health issues before they occur. Others propose
702 comprehensive iron status evaluations in children before each vaccination to prevent severe
703 aluminum-related side effects. [\[179, 180\]](#)

704 Discussion and conclusion

705 If vaccination is one of the greatest achievements in the history of medicine, and while
706 vaccines are tolerated by much of the population, the risks of adverse reactions—particularly
707 to aluminum-based adjuvants—among specific populations have raised concerns and sparked
708 controversy for decades. [\[80, 99, 184, 185\]](#)

709 In France, 8 out of the 11 mandatory vaccines, which often require multiple doses, contain
710 aluminum adjuvants. The quantity of aluminum administered before a child reaches 12
711 months of age continues to increase. [\[98\]](#)

712 Current scientific knowledge should prompt us to act swiftly to assess the safety of aluminum-
713 based adjuvants [\[186\]](#). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), iron deficiency is
714 the most widespread nutritional disorder globally. It affects 30% of the population, with
715 reduced iron absorption being one of the contributing factors to its high prevalence. As we
716 have seen in this article, interactions between iron and aluminum could be one of the causes
717 of this iron deficiency epidemic. [\[187\]](#)

718 Moreover, the emerging understanding of the interplay between iron metabolism, genetic
719 predispositions such as hereditary hemochromatosis, and aluminum accumulation raises
720 important clinical and therapeutic considerations. Patients with genetic variants affecting iron
721 regulation may inadvertently experience a higher retention of aluminum, exacerbating
722 inflammatory pathologies like macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF). The role of macrophages in
723 iron and aluminum metabolism, combined with processes such as autophagy and ferroptosis,
724 highlights the complexity of these interactions and the need for targeted diagnostic and
725 therapeutic approaches.

726 Beyond MMF, the potential implications of aluminum accumulation extend to other
727 inflammatory and neurodegenerative diseases, which share overlapping pathways of iron
728 dysregulation and oxidative stress. This underscores the necessity of further interdisciplinary
729 research to clarify these mechanisms and their clinical relevance.

730 My hope in writing this article is that these new insights into the genetic predisposition to
731 retain iron—and very likely aluminum—will encourage vaccine manufacturers to offer
732 alternatives with non-toxic adjuvants, such as calcium phosphate, which has been successfully
733 used in the past. Additionally, I hope this work will prompt the medical and scientific
734 community to adopt a more personalized approach to vaccination, particularly for individuals
735 genetically predisposed to iron dysregulation. A collaborative effort between clinicians,
736 researchers, and policymakers is essential to ensure that the benefits of vaccination remain
737 universally accessible while minimizing adverse effects in vulnerable populations.

738

739 A complementary case report illustrating these hypotheses in a genetically predisposed
740 patient is available in a preprint:

741 Guénola G. (2024). Case Report: A Complex Interaction Between Vaccination-Related
742 Macrophagic Myofasciitis, Iron Overload, and Genetic Variants in TFR2 and SLC40A1. Preprint
743 available on Zenodo. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15315967

744 Conflict of Interest Statement

745 The author declares no financial or institutional conflict of interest. However, she has been
746 diagnosed with macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF), which motivated her interest in this topic.
747 This personal context did not influence the interpretation of scientific data presented in this
748 work.

749 Appendix

750 Table of genes involved in iron metabolism

Gènes	Rôle
HFE	Codes for the HFE protein, which regulates iron absorption by interacting with transferrin receptors (TfR1 and TfR2). Mutations in this gene are responsible for type 1 hereditary hemochromatosis.
TFR1 Transferrin Receptor 1	Codes for transferrin receptor 1, which is responsible for iron uptake into cells via endocytosis of the iron-transferrin complex.
TFR2 Transferrin Receptor 2	Codes for transferrin receptor 2, essential for regulating iron absorption and hepcidin

	production. Mutations in this gene cause type 3 hereditary hemochromatosis.
HJV Hemojuvelin	Codes for a protein involved in BMP (Bone Morphogenetic Protein) signaling, which activates hepcidin expression. Mutations in this gene cause juvenile hemochromatosis.
HAMP Hepcidin Antimicrobial Peptide	Codes for hepcidin, a key hormone that regulates iron absorption and controls the amount of iron released into the blood. Mutations in this gene can lead to juvenile hemochromatosis.
SLC40A1 Solute Carrier Family 40 Member 1	Codes for ferroportin, a protein responsible for exporting iron from cells into the plasma. Mutations in this gene can cause disorders such as "ferroportin disease."
BMP6 Bone Morphogenetic Protein 6	Involvement in BMP signaling, activating hepcidin expression. This gene is essential for regulating hepcidin production in response to iron levels.
TMPRSS6 Transmembrane Serine Protease 6	Codes for the matriptase-2 protease, which inhibits hepcidin production by regulating BMP signaling. Mutations can cause refractory iron-deficiency anemia.
FPN1 Ferroportin 1	Codes for ferroportin (like SLC40A1), regulating the release of iron from cells into the bloodstream. Mutations in this gene lead to iron overload disorders.
DMT1 Divalent Metal Transporter 1 ou SLC11A2	Transports iron into cells, primarily at the level of intestinal enterocytes for absorption and in macrophages for iron recycling.
FTH1 Ferritin Heavy Chain 1	Codes for the ferritin heavy chain, a protein for storing iron in cells.
FTL Ferritin Light Chain	Codes for the ferritin light chain, which stores and releases iron in a controlled manner.
CYBRD1 Cytochrome b Reductase 1	Codes for an enzyme involved in the reduction of non-heme iron, facilitating its absorption in the intestine.
ALOX15 Arachidonate 15-Lipoxygenase	Involvement in the release of iron from ferritin in macrophages, aiding in iron recycling.
STEAP3 Six-Transmembrane Epithelial Antigen of Prostate 3	Reduces ferric iron (Fe ³⁺) to ferrous iron (Fe ²⁺), facilitating its transport by DMT1.
GNPAT Glyceronephosphate O-Acyltransferase	Gene associated with certain forms of refractory anemias, although its role in iron

regulation is not directly linked to hepcidin or ferroportin.

751

752 Références

753

754 1 - Crichton R. The importance of iron in biological systems. In: Crichton R, editor. Inorganic
755 Chemistry of Iron Metabolism. Chichester: John Wiley and Sons; 2001. p. 17–45.
756 doi:10.1002/0470845791.ch2.

757 2 - Chifman J, Laubenbacher R, Torti SV. A systems biology approach to iron metabolism. *Adv*
758 *Exp Med Biol.* 2014;844:201–225. doi:10.1007/978-1-4939-2095-2_10. PMID: 25480643;
759 PMCID: PMC4464783.

760 3 - Roemhild K, von Maltzahn F, Weiskirchen R, Knüchel R, von Stillfried S, Lammers T. Iron
761 metabolism: pathophysiology and pharmacology. *Trends Pharmacol Sci.* 2021;42(8):640–656.
762 doi:10.1016/j.tips.2021.05.001. PMID: 34090703; PMCID: PMC7611894.

763 4 - Brissot P, Loréal O. Iron metabolism and related genetic diseases: a cleared land, keeping
764 mysteries. *J Hepatol.* 2016;64(2):505–515. doi:10.1016/j.jhep.2015.11.009.

765 5 - Del-Castillo-Rueda A, Moreno-Carralero MI, Cuadrado-Grande N, Alvarez-Sala-Walther LA,
766 Enríquez-de-Salamanca R, Méndez M, Morán-Jiménez MJ. Mutations in the HFE, TFR2, and
767 SLC40A1 genes in patients with hemochromatosis. *Gene.* 2012;508(1):15–20.
768 doi:10.1016/j.gene.2012.07.069. PMID: 22890139.

769 6 - Ulvik RJ. Hereditary haemochromatosis through 150 years. *Tidsskr Nor Lægeforen.*
770 2016;136(21):2017–2021. doi:10.4045/tidsskr.15.1003.

771 7 - Ruivard M, Lobbes H. Diagnostic et traitement d'une surcharge en fer [Diagnosis and
772 treatment of iron overload]. *Rev Med Interne.* 2023;44(12):656–661.
773 doi:10.1016/j.revmed.2023.07.002. PMID: 37507250.

774 8 - Pantopoulos K. Inherited disorders of iron overload. *Front Nutr.* 2018;5:103.
775 doi:10.3389/fnut.2018.00103. PMID: 30420953; PMCID: PMC6215844.

776 9 - Piperno A, Pelucchi S, Mariani R. Inherited iron overload disorders. *Transl Gastroenterol*
777 *Hepatol.* 2020;5:25. doi:10.21037/tgh.2019.11.15. PMID: 32258529; PMCID: PMC7063521.

778 10 – Pietrangelo A. Ferroportin disease: pathogenesis, diagnosis and treatment.
779 *Haematologica.* 2017;102(12):1972–1984. doi:10.3324/haematol.2017.170720. PMID:
780 29101207; PMCID: PMC5709096.

781 11 - Uguen K, Le Tertre M, Tchernitchko D, Elbahnsi A, Maestri S, Gourlaouen I, Férec C, Ka C,
782 Callebaut I, Le Gac G. The dual loss and gain of function of the FPN1 iron exporter results in
783 the ferroportin disease phenotype. *HGG Adv.* 2024;5(4):100335.
784 doi:10.1016/j.xhgg.2024.100335. PMID: 39039793; PMCID: PMC11343060.

- 785 12 - Meynard D, Kautz L, Darnaud V, Canonne-Hergaux F, Coppin H, Roth MP. Lack of the bone
786 morphogenetic protein BMP6 induces massive iron overload. *Nat Genet.* 2009;41(4):478–81.
787 doi:10.1038/ng.320. PMID: 19252488.
- 788 13 - Daher R, Kannengiesser C, Houamel D, Lefebvre T, Bardou-Jacquet E, Ducrot N, de
789 Kerguenec C, Jouanolle AM, Robreau AM, Oudin C, Le Gac G, Moulouel B, Loustaud-Ratti V,
790 Bedossa P, Valla D, Gouya L, Beaumont C, Brissot P, Puy H, Karim Z, Tchernitchko D.
791 Heterozygous mutations in BMP6 pro-peptide lead to inappropriate hepcidin synthesis and
792 moderate iron overload in humans. *Gastroenterology.* 2016;150(3):672–683.e4.
793 doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2015.10.049. PMID: 26582087.
- 794 14 - Njajou OT, Vaessen N, Joosse M, Berghuis B, van Dongen JW, Breuning MH, Snijders PJ,
795 Rutten WP, Sandkuijl LA, Oostra BA, van Duijn CM, Heutink P. A mutation in SLC11A3 is
796 associated with autosomal dominant hemochromatosis. *Nat Genet.* 2001;28(3):213–214.
797 doi:10.1038/90038. PMID: 11431687.
- 798 15 - Njajou OT, de Jong G, Berghuis B, Vaessen N, Snijders PJ, Goossens JP, Wilson JH,
799 Breuning MH, Oostra BA, Heutink P, Sandkuijl LA, van Duijn CM. Dominant hemochromatosis
800 due to N144H mutation of SLC11A3: clinical and biological characteristics. *Blood Cells Mol*
801 *Dis.* 2002;29(3):439–443. doi:10.1006/bcmd.2002.0581. PMID: 12547233.
- 802 16 - Cappellini MD, Comin-Colet J, de Francisco A, Dignass A, Doehner W, Lam CS,
803 Macdougall IC, Rogler G, Camaschella C, Kadir R, Kassebaum NJ, Spahn DR, Taher AT,
804 Musallam KM; IRON CORE Group. Iron deficiency across chronic inflammatory conditions:
805 International expert opinion on definition, diagnosis, and management. *Am J Hematol.*
806 2017;92(10):1068–1078. doi:10.1002/ajh.24820. PMID: 28612425; PMCID: PMC5599965.
- 807 17 - Zhang Z, Hou L, Song JL, Song N, Sun YJ, Lin X, Wang XL, Zhang FZ, Ge YL. Pro-
808 inflammatory cytokine-mediated ferroportin down-regulation contributes to the nigral iron
809 accumulation in lipopolysaccharide-induced Parkinsonian models. *Neuroscience.*
810 2014;257:20–30. doi:10.1016/j.neuroscience.2013.09.037. PMID: 24183966.
- 811 18 - Pang N, Ding M, Yang H, Zhong Q, Zheng L, Luo D, Yao Y. Iron overload causes
812 macrophages to produce a pro-inflammatory phenotype in the synovium of hemophiliac
813 arthritis via the acetyl-p53 pathway. *Haemophilia.* 2024;30(1):195–203.
814 doi:10.1111/hae.14905. PMID: 38058260.
- 815 19 - Nairz M, Weiss G. Iron in infection and immunity. *Mol Aspects Med.* 2020;75:100864.
816 doi:10.1016/j.mam.2020.100864. PMID: 32461004.
- 817 20 - Kowdley KV. Iron overload in patients with chronic liver disease. *Gastroenterol Hepatol*
818 *(N Y).* 2016;12(11):695–698. PMID: 28035198; PMCID: PMC5193089.
- 819 21 - Melas N, Stål P. **Hyperferritinemi – utredning, diagnos och behandling**
820 **[Hyperferritinemia - investigation, diagnosis and treatment].** *Lakartidningen.* 2024 Oct
821 **8;121:24008. Swedish. PMID: 39411810.**

- 822 22 - Sachinidis A, Doumas M, Imprialos K, Stavropoulos K, Katsimardou A, Athyros VG.
823 **Dysmetabolic iron overload in metabolic syndrome. *Curr Pharm Des.* 2020;26(10):1019–**
824 **1024. doi:10.2174/1381612826666200130090703. PMID: 32000639.**
- 825 23 - He H, Liao S, Zeng Y, Liang L, Chen J, Tao C. Causal relationships between metabolic-
826 associated fatty liver disease and iron status: Two-sample Mendelian randomization. *Liver*
827 *Int.* 2022;42(12):2759–2768. doi:10.1111/liv.15455. PMID: 36226474.
- 828 24 - Millot S, Delaby C, Moulouel B, Lefebvre T, Pilard N, Ducrot N, Ged C, Lettéron P, de
829 Franceschi L, Deybach JC, Beaumont C, Gouya L, De Verneuil H, Lyoumi S, Puy H, Karim Z.
830 **Hemolytic anemia repressed hepcidin level without hepatocyte iron overload: lesson from**
831 **Günther disease model. *Haematologica.* 2017;102(2):260–270.**
832 **doi:10.3324/haematol.2016.151621. PMID: 28143953; PMCID: PMC5286934.**
- 833 25 - Lyle L, Hirose A. Iron overload in myelodysplastic syndromes: pathophysiology,
834 consequences, diagnosis, and treatment. *J Adv Pract Oncol.* 2018;9(4):392–405. PMID:
835 **30719392; PMCID: PMC6347085.**
- 836 26 - Wood JC. Diagnosis and management of transfusion iron overload: the role of imaging.
837 *Am J Hematol.* 2007;82(12 Suppl):1132–1135. doi:10.1002/ajh.21099. PMID: 17963249;
838 PMCID: PMC2892928.
- 839 27 - Cirovic A, Cirovic A, Orisakwe OE, Lima RR. Local and systemic hypoxia as inductors of
840 increased aluminum and iron brain accumulation promoting the onset of Alzheimer’s
841 disease. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2023;201(11):5134–5142. doi:10.1007/s12011-023-03599-y.
842 PMID: 36757557.
- 843 28 – Ioannou GN, Dominitz JA, Weiss NS, Heagerty PJ, Kowdley KV. The effect of alcohol
844 consumption on the prevalence of iron overload, iron deficiency, and iron deficiency anemia.
845 *Gastroenterology.* 2004 May;126(5):1293-301. doi: 10.1053/j.gastro.2004.01.020. PMID:
846 15131790.
- 847 29 - Topiwala A, Wang C, Ebmeier KP, Burgess S, Bell S, Levey DF, Zhou H, McCracken C, Roca-
848 Fernández A, Petersen SE, Raman B, Husain M, Gelernter J, et al. Associations between
849 moderate alcohol consumption, brain iron, and cognition in UK Biobank participants:
850 Observational and Mendelian randomization analyses. *PLoS Med.* 2022;19(7):e1004039.
851 doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1004039.
- 852 30 - Dichtl S, Haschka D, Nairz M, Seifert M, Volani C, Lutz O, Weiss G. Dopamine promotes
853 cellular iron accumulation and oxidative stress responses in macrophages. *Biochem*
854 *Pharmacol.* 2018;148:193–201. doi:10.1016/j.bcp.2017.12.001.
- 855 31 – Hare D, Ayton S, Bush A, Lei P. A delicate balance: Iron metabolism and diseases of the
856 brain. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2013 Jul 18;5:34. doi: 10.3389/fnagi.2013.00034. PMID:
857 23874300
- 858 32 - Melicene S, Peoc’h K, Ducastel M. Exploration of iron metabolism: what is new? *J Lab*
859 *Precis Med.* 2021;6:Article 6. doi: 10.21037/jlpm-21-50

860 33 - Truong J, Naveed K, Beriault D, Lightfoot D, Fralick M, Sholzberg M. The origin of ferritin
861 reference intervals: a systematic review. *Lancet Haematol.* 2024;11(7):e530–e539.
862 doi:10.1016/S2352-3026(24)00103-0. PMID: 38937026.

863 34 - Parida A, Behera RK. Iron accumulation in ferritin. In: *Methods Mol Biol.* 2023;2671:121–
864 134. doi:10.1007/978-1-0716-3222-2_7. PMID: 37308642.

865 35 - Stack AG, Mutwali AI, Nguyen HT, Cronin CJ, Casserly LF, Ferguson J. Transferrin
866 saturation ratio and risk of total and cardiovascular mortality in the general population. *QJM.*
867 2014;107(8):623–633. doi:10.1093/qjmed/hcu045. PMID: 24599805

868 36 - Elsayed ME, Sharif MU, Stack AG. Transferrin Saturation: A Body Iron Biomarker. *Adv Clin*
869 *Chem.* 2016;75:71-97. doi: 10.1016/bs.acc.2016.03.002. PMID: 27346617.

870 37 - Varghese A, Thomas SM. Iron deficiency anemia, anemia of chronic disease, iron
871 overload: Use of hepcidin as a laboratory marker in the diagnosis along with its therapeutic
872 implications and management of iron homeostasis. *Clin Lab Med.* DOI:
873 10.29322/IJSRP.12.12.2022.p13224

874 38 - Muñoz M, García-Erce JA, Remacha ÁF. Disorders of iron metabolism. Part II: iron
875 deficiency and iron overload. *J Clin Pathol.* 2011;64(4):287–296.
876 doi:10.1136/jcp.2010.086371. PMID: 21177268.

877 39 - Camaschella C, Nai A, Silvestri L. Iron metabolism and iron disorders revisited in the
878 hepcidin era. *Haematologica.* 2020 Jan 31;105(2):260-272. doi:
879 10.3324/haematol.2019.232124. PMID: 31949017

880 40 - Garcia-Casal MN, Pasricha SR, Martinez RX, Lopez-Perez L, Peña-Rosas JP. Serum or
881 plasma ferritin concentration as an index of iron deficiency and overload. *Cochrane Database*
882 *Syst Rev.* 2021 May 24;5(5):CD011817. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD011817.pub2. PMID:
883 34028001

884 41 - Brissot P, Pietrangelo A, Adams PC, de Graaff B, McLaren CE, Loréal O.
885 Haemochromatosis. *Nat Rev Dis Primers.* 2018 Apr 5;4:18016. doi: 10.1038/nrdp.2018.16.
886 PMID: 29620054

887 42 - Kwo PY, Cohen SM, Lim JK. ACG clinical guideline: evaluation of abnormal liver
888 chemistries. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2017;112(1):18–35. doi:10.1038/ajg.2016.517.

889 43 - d'Assignies G, Paisant A, Bardou-Jacquet E, Boulic A, Bannier E, Lainé F, et al. Non-
890 invasive measurement of liver iron concentration using 3-Tesla magnetic resonance imaging:
891 validation against biopsy. *Eur Radiol.* 2018;28(5):2022–2030. doi:10.1007/s00330-017-5106-
892 3. PMID: 29178028

893 44 - Wood JC. Estimating tissue iron burden: current status and future prospects. *Br J*
894 *Haematol.* 2015 Jul;170(1):15-28. doi: 10.1111/bjh.13374. PMID: 25765344

895 45 - França M, Martí-Bonmatí L, Silva S, Oliveira C, Alberich Bayarri Á, Vilas Boas F,
896 Pessegueiro-Miranda H, Porto G. Optimizing the management of hereditary

897 haemochromatosis: the value of MRI R2* quantification to predict and monitor body iron
898 stores. *Br J Haematol.* 2018 Nov;183(3):491-493. doi: 10.1111/bjh.14982. PMID: 29082508.

899 46 - Legros L, Bardou-Jacquet E, Latournerie M, Guillygomarc'h A, Turlin B, Le Lan C, Désille Y,
900 Lainé F, Moirand R, Brissot P, Deugnier Y, Guyader D. Non-invasive assessment of liver fibrosis
901 in C282Y homozygous HFE hemochromatosis. *Liver Int.* 2015 Jun;35(6):1731-8. doi:
902 10.1111/liv.12762. PMID: 25495562.

903 47 - European Association for the Study of the Liver. Electronic address:
904 easloffice@easloffice.eu; European Association for the Study of the Liver. EASL Clinical
905 Practice Guidelines on haemochromatosis. *J Hepatol.* 2022 Aug;77(2):479-502. doi:
906 10.1016/j.jhep.2022.03.033. Erratum in: *J Hepatol.* 2023 Nov;79(5):1341. doi:
907 10.1016/j.jhep.2023.09.002. PMID: 35662478.

908 48 - Loréal O, Cavey T, Bardou-Jacquet E, Guggenbuhl P, Ropert M, Brissot P. Iron, hepcidin,
909 and the metal connection. *Front Pharmacol.* 2014 Jun 4;5:128. doi:
910 10.3389/fphar.2014.00128. PMID: 24926268

911 49 - Deshpande CN, Ruwe TA, Shawki A, Xin V, Vieth KR, Valore EV, Qiao B, Ganz T, Nemeth E,
912 Mackenzie B, Jormakka M. Calcium is an essential cofactor for metal efflux by the ferroportin
913 transporter family. *Nat Commun.* 2018 Aug 6;9(1):3075. doi: 10.1038/s41467-018-05446-4.
914 PMID: 30082682

915 50 - Hopkins MR, Ettinger AS, Hernández-Avila M, Schwartz J, Téllez-Rojo MM, Lamadrid-
916 Figueroa H, Bellinger D, Hu H, Wright RO. Variants in iron metabolism genes predict higher
917 blood lead levels in young children. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2008 Sep;116(9):1261-6. doi:
918 10.1289/ehp.11233. PMID: 18795173

919 51 - Kim KN, Lee MR, Lim YH, Hong YC. Blood lead levels, iron metabolism gene
920 polymorphisms and homocysteine: a gene-environment interaction study. *Occup Environ*
921 *Med.* 2017 Dec;74(12):899-904. doi: 10.1136/oemed-2017-104375. PMID: 28775131.

922 52 - Onalaja AO, Claudio L. Genetic susceptibility to lead poisoning. *Environ Health Perspect.*
923 2000 Mar;108 Suppl 1(Suppl 1):23-8. doi: 10.1289/ehp.00108s123. PMID: 10698721

924 53 - Gomes WR, Devóz PP, Luiz BLC, Grotto D, Batista BL, Barbosa F Jr, Barcelos GRM.
925 Polymorphisms of genes related to metabolism of lead (Pb) are associated with the metal body
926 burden and with biomarkers of oxidative stress. *Mutat Res Genet Toxicol Environ Mutagen.* 2018
927 Dec;836(Pt B):42-46. doi: 10.1016/j.mrgentox.2018.05.016. PMID: 30442344.

928 54 - Cuomo D, Nitcher M, Barba E, Feinberg AP, Rusyn I, Chiu WA, Threadgill DW. Refining risk
929 estimates for lead in drinking water based on the impact of genetics and diet on blood lead
930 levels using the Collaborative Cross mouse population. *Toxicol Sci.* 2023 Jul 28;194(2):226-
931 234. doi: 10.1093/toxsci/kfad054. PMID: 37243727

932 55 - Cuomo D, Foster MJ, Threadgill D. Systemic review of genetic and epigenetic factors
933 underlying differential toxicity to environmental lead (Pb) exposure. *Environ Sci Pollut Res*
934 *Int.* 2022 May;29(24):35583-35598. doi: 10.1007/s11356-022-19333-5. PMID: 35244845

935 56 - Beardmore J, Rugg G, Exley C. A systems biology approach to the blood-aluminium
936 problem: the application and testing of a computational model. *J Inorg Biochem.* 2007
937 Sep;101(9):1187-91. doi: 10.1016/j.jinorgbio.2007.06.015 PMID: 17629565.

938 57 - Trapp GA. Plasma aluminum is bound to transferrin. *Life Sci.* 1983 Jul 25;33(4):311-6.
939 doi: 10.1016/s0024-3205(83)80002-2. PMID: 6410138.

940 58 - McGregor SJ, Naves ML, Oria R, Vass JK, Brock JH. Effect of aluminium on iron uptake and
941 transferrin-receptor expression by human erythroleukaemia K562 cells. *Biochem J.* 1990 Dec
942 1;272(2):377-82. doi: 10.1042/bj2720377. PMID: 2268267

943 59 - Pérez G, Pregi N, Vittori D, Di Risio C, Garbossa G, Nesse A. Aluminum exposure affects
944 transferrin-dependent and -independent iron uptake by K562 cells. *Biochim Biophys Acta.*
945 2005 Aug 15;1745(1):124-30. doi: 10.1016/j.bbamcr.2004.12.002. PMID: 16085060.

946 60 - Christopher Exley, Matthew J. Mold, The binding, transport and fate of aluminium in
947 biological cells, *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*, Volume 30, 2015, Pages
948 90-95, ISSN 0946-672X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2014.11.002>.

949 61 - J. B. Cannata, C. Gómez Alonso, M. J. Fernández Menéndez, I. Fernández Soto, S.
950 McGregor, P. Menéndez-Fraga, J. H. Brock, Iron Uptake in Aluminium Overload: In Vivo and In
951 Vitro Studies, *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*, Volume 6, Issue 9, 1991, Pages 637–642,
952 <https://doi.org/10.1093/ndt/6.9.637> PMID: 1745387.

953 62 - Huang JY, Huang CC, Lim PS, Wu MS, Leu ML. Effect of body iron stores on serum
954 aluminum level in hemodialysis patients. *Nephron.* 1992;61(2):158-62. doi:
955 10.1159/000186864. PMID: 1630539.

956 63 - Jorge B. Cannata, Isabel Fernández-Soto, María J. Fernández-Menendez, José L.
957 Fernández-Martín, Sheila J. McGregor, Jeremy H. Brock, David Halls, Role of iron metabolism
958 in absorption and cellular uptake of aluminum, *Kidney International*, Volume 39, Issue 4,
959 1991, Pages 799-803, ISSN 0085-2538, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ki.1991.98>. PMID: 2051739.

960 64 - Van Landeghem GF, D'Haese PC, Lamberts LV, Djukanovic L, Pejanovic S, Goodman WG,
961 De Broe ME. Low serum aluminum values in dialysis patients with increased bone aluminum
962 levels. *Clin Nephrol.* 1998 Aug;50(2):69-76. PMID: 9725776.

963 65 - Ward RJ, Zhang Y, Crichton RR. Aluminium toxicity and iron homeostasis. *J Inorg*
964 *Biochem.* 2001 Nov;87(1-2):9-14. doi: 10.1016/s0162-0134(01)00308-7. PMID: 11709207.

965 66 - Kim Y, Olivi L, Cheong JH, Maertens A, Bressler JP. Aluminum stimulates uptake of non-
966 transferrin bound iron and transferrin bound iron in human glial cells. *Toxicol Appl*
967 *Pharmacol.* 2007 May 1;220(3):349-56. doi: 10.1016/j.taap.2007.02.001. PMID: 17376497;

968 67 - Congrès de la Société française de recherche sur le sommeil, Strasbourg, octobre 2002
969 *Neurophysiologie clinique* 33 (2003) 33–53 <http://sommeil2002.free.fr/Resume.htm>

970 68 - Manconi M, Fabbrini M, Bonanni E, Filippi M, Rocca M, Murri L, Ferini-Strambi L. High
971 prevalence of restless legs syndrome in multiple sclerosis. *Eur J Neurol.* 2007 May;14(5):534-
972 9. doi: 10.1111/j.1468-1331.2007.01740.x. PMID: 17437613.

- 973 69 - Pascazio A, Maestri M, Pasquali L, Hoxhaj D, Fabbrini M, Furfori G, Ulivi M, Bianchi F,
974 Morganti R, Siciliano G, Bonanni E. Restless Legs Syndrome and fatigue in multiple sclerosis:
975 A cross-sectional clinical study. *Mult Scler Relat Disord*. 2023 Nov;79:104946. doi:
976 10.1016/j.msard.2023.104946. PMID: 37639779.
- 977 70 - Trotti LM, Becker LA. Iron for the treatment of restless legs syndrome. *Cochrane*
978 *Database Syst Rev*. 2019 Jan 4;1(1):CD007834. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD007834.pub3.
979 PMID: 30609006
- 980 71 - Connor JR, Patton SM, Oexle K, Allen RP. Iron and restless legs syndrome: treatment,
981 genetics and pathophysiology. *Sleep Med*. 2017 Mar;31:61-70. doi:
982 10.1016/j.sleep.2016.07.028. PMID: 28057495
- 983 72 - Cirovic A, Cirovic A, Orisakwe OE, Lima RR. Local and Systemic Hypoxia as Inductors of
984 Increased Aluminum and Iron Brain Accumulation Promoting the Onset of Alzheimer's
985 Disease. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2023 Nov;201(11):5134-5142. doi: 10.1007/s12011-023-03599-
986 y. Epub 2023 Feb 9. PMID: 36757557.
- 987 73 - Zhang Z, Hou L, Song JL, Song N, Sun YJ, Lin X, Wang XL, Zhang FZ, Ge YL. Pro-
988 inflammatory cytokine-mediated ferroportin down-regulation contributes to the nigral iron
989 accumulation in lipopolysaccharide-induced Parkinsonian models. *Neuroscience*. 2014 Jan
990 17;257:20-30. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2013.09.037. PMID: 24183966.
- 991 74 - Ganz T. 2016. Macrophages and Iron Metabolism. *Microbiol Spectr*
992 4:10.1128/microbiolspec.mchd-0037-2016. [https://doi.org/10.1128/microbiolspec.mchd-
993 0037-2016](https://doi.org/10.1128/microbiolspec.mchd-0037-2016)
- 994 75 - Masson, JD., Badran, G., Domdom, M.A. et al. Advances on the early cellular events
995 occurring upon exposure of human macrophages to aluminum oxyhydroxide adjuvant. *Sci*
996 *Rep* 13, 3198 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-30336-1>
- 997 76 - Glick D, Barth S, Macleod KF. Autophagy: cellular and molecular mechanisms. *J Pathol*.
998 2010 May;221(1):3-12. doi: 10.1002/path.2697. PMID: 20225336
- 999 77 - Ichimiya T, Yamakawa T, Hirano T, Yokoyama Y, Hayashi Y, Hirayama D, Wagatsuma K, Itoi
1000 T, Nakase H. Autophagy and Autophagy-Related Diseases: A Review. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020 Nov
1001 26;21(23):8974. doi: 10.3390/ijms21238974. PMID: 33255983
- 1002 78 - Bagherniya M, Butler AE, Barreto GE, Sahebkar A. The effect of fasting or calorie
1003 restriction on autophagy induction: A review of the literature. *Ageing Res Rev*. 2018
1004 Nov;47:183-197. doi: 10.1016/j.arr.2018.08.004. PMID: 30172870.
- 1005 79 - D'Arcy MS. Cell death: a review of the major forms of apoptosis, necrosis and autophagy.
1006 *Cell Biol Int*. 2019 Jun;43(6):582-592. doi: 10.1002/cbin.11137. PMID: 30958602.
- 1007 80 - Romain K, Gherardi, Guillemette Crépeaux, François-Jérôme Authier, Myalgia and
1008 chronic fatigue syndrome following immunization: macrophagic myofasciitis and animal
1009 studies support linkage to aluminum adjuvant persistency and diffusion in the immune
1010 system, *Autoimmunity Reviews*, doi.org/10.1016/j.autrev.2019.05.006. PMID: 31059838.

- 1011 81 - Wardman P, Candeias LP. Fenton chemistry: an introduction. *Radiat Res.* 1996
1012 May;145(5):523-31. PMID: 8619017.
- 1013 82 - Bogdan AR, Miyazawa M, Hashimoto K, Tsuji Y. Regulators of Iron Homeostasis: New
1014 Players in Metabolism, Cell Death, and Disease. *Trends Biochem Sci.* 2016 Mar;41(3):274-
1015 286. doi: 10.1016/j.tibs.2015.11.012. PMID: 26725301
- 1016 83 - Lee S, Hwang N, Seok BG, Lee S, Lee SJ, Chung SW. Autophagy mediates an amplification
1017 loop during ferroptosis. *Cell Death Dis.* 2023 Jul 25;14(7):464. doi: 10.1038/s41419-023-
1018 05978-8. PMID: 37491375
- 1019 84 - Yan HF, Zou T, Tuo QZ, Xu S, Li H, Belaidi AA, Lei P. Ferroptosis: mechanisms and links with
1020 diseases. *Signal Transduct Target Ther.* 2021 Feb 3;6(1):49. doi: 10.1038/s41392-020-00428-
1021 9. PMID: 33536413
- 1022 85 - Reichert CO, de Freitas FA, Sampaio-Silva J, Rokita-Rosa L, Barros PL, Levy D, Bydlowski
1023 SP. Ferroptosis Mechanisms Involved in Neurodegenerative Diseases. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2020 Nov
1024 20;21(22):8765. doi: 10.3390/ijms21228765. PMID: 33233496
- 1025 86 - Dale Viezeliene & Aldona Baltusnikiene & Piet Beekhof & Rima Naginiene & Dale
1026 Baranauskiene, 2022. "Aluminium Induces Iron-Mediated Oxidative Stress in Brain Tissue,"
1027 *Biomedical Journal of Scientific & Technical Research, Biomedical Research Network+, LLC,*
1028 vol. 42(4), pages 33762-33767, March. doi: 10.26717/BJSTR.2022.42.006771
- 1029 87 - Chatterjee S, Sarkar S, Bhattacharya S. Toxic metals and autophagy. *Chem Res Toxicol.*
1030 2014 Nov 17;27(11):1887-900. doi: 10.1021/tx500264s. PMID: 25310621.
- 1031 88 - Li Q, Feng Y, Wang R, Liu R, Ba Y, Huang H. Recent insights into autophagy and
1032 metals/nanoparticles exposure. *Toxicol Res.* 2023 May 19;39(3):355-372. doi:
1033 10.1007/s43188-023-00184-2. PMID: 37398566
- 1034 89 - Masson JD, Badran G, Gherardi RK, Authier FJ, Crépeaux G. Widespread Myalgia and
1035 Chronic Fatigue: Phagocytes from Macrophagic Myofasciitis Patients Exposed to Aluminum
1036 Oxyhydroxide-Adjuvanted Vaccine Exhibit Specific Inflammatory, Autophagic, and
1037 Mitochondrial Responses. *Toxics.* 2024 Jul 4;12(7):491. doi: 10.3390/toxics12070491. PMID:
1038 39058143
- 1039 90 - Nakamura, S., Oba, M., Suzuki, M. et al. Suppression of autophagic activity by Rubicon is
1040 a signature of aging. *Nat Commun* 10, 847 (2019). [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08729-6)
1041 08729-6 PMID: 30783089
- 1042 91 - Jahng JWS, Alsaadi RM, Palanivel R, Song E, Hipolito VEB, Sung HK, Botelho RJ, Russell
1043 RC, Sweeney G. Iron overload inhibits late stage autophagic flux leading to insulin resistance.
1044 *EMBO Rep.* 2019 Oct 4;20(10):e47911. doi: 10.15252/embr.201947911. PMID: 31441223
- 1045 92 - Deqiang Fu, Xingyue Liang, Yuxuan Jiang, Jieping Liu, Xiaosi Lin, Quan Yang, Xue Chen,
1046 Ping Huang, Wei Wang, Wenlin Wu, Iron blocks autophagic flux and induces
1047 autophagosomes accumulation in microglia, *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, Volume 181,
1048 2023, 114054, ISSN 0278-6915, doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2023.114054 PMID: 37777083.

1049 93 - Krishan S, Jansson PJ, Gutierrez E, Lane DJ, Richardson D, Sahni S. IRON METABOLISM
1050 AND AUTOPHAGY: A POORLY EXPLORED RELATIONSHIP THAT HAS IMPORTANT
1051 CONSEQUENCES FOR HEALTH AND DISEASE. *Nagoya J Med Sci.* 2015 Feb;77(1-2):1-6. PMID:
1052 25797965

1053 94 - Wang Y, Wang M, Liu Y, Tao H, Banerjee S, Srinivasan S, Nemeth E, Czaja MJ, He P.
1054 Integrated regulation of stress responses, autophagy and survival by altered intracellular iron
1055 stores. *Redox Biol.* 2022 Sep;55:102407. doi: 10.1016/j.redox.2022.102407. PMID: 35853304

1056 95 - Van Landeghem GF, D'Haese PC, Lamberts LV, De Broe ME. Competition of iron and
1057 aluminum for transferrin: the molecular basis for aluminum deposition in iron-overloaded
1058 dialysis patients? *Exp Nephrol.* 1997 May-Jun;5(3):239-45. PMID: 9208284.

1059 96 - Exley C. An aluminium adjuvant in a vaccine is an acute exposure to aluminium. *J Trace*
1060 *Elem Med Biol.* 2020 Jan;57:57-59. doi: 10.1016/j.jtemb.2019.09.010. PMID: 31561170.

1061 97 - James Lyons-Weiler, Robert Ricketson, Reconsideration of the immunotherapeutic
1062 pediatric safe dose levels of aluminum, *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*,
1063 Volume 48, 2018, Pages 67-73,ISSN 0946-672X,
1064 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2018.02.025>. PMID: 29773196.

1065 98 - Angrand L, Elnar AA, Authier FJ, Gherardi RK, Crépeaux G. Exposition à l'aluminium
1066 vaccinal en France en 2018 [Aluminium adjuvant exposure through vaccines in France in
1067 2018]. *Ann Pharm Fr.* 2020 Mar;78(2):111-128. French. doi: 10.1016/j.pharma.2020.01.002.
1068 Epub 2020 Jan 17. Erratum in: *Ann Pharm Fr.* 2020 Nov;78(6):544-545. doi:
1069 10.1016/j.pharma.2020.07.008. PMID: 32081303.

1070 99 - Shaw CA, Li D, Tomljenovic L. Are there negative CNS impacts of aluminum adjuvants
1071 used in vaccines and immunotherapy? *Immunotherapy.* 2014;6(10):1055-71. doi:
1072 10.2217/imt.14.81. Erratum in: *Immunotherapy.* 2019 Apr;11(6):555. doi:
1073 10.2217/imt.14.81c1. PMID: 25428645.

1074 100 - Yokel RA, McNamara PJ. Aluminium toxicokinetics: an updated minireview. *Pharmacol*
1075 *Toxicol.* 2001 Apr;88(4):159-67. doi: 10.1034/j.1600-0773.2001.d01-98.x. PMID: 11322172.

1076 101 - Guis S, Mattei JP, Nicoli F, Pellissier JF, Kaplanski G, Figarella-Branger D, et al. Identical
1077 twins with macrophagic myofasciitis: genetic susceptibility and triggering by aluminic vaccine
1078 adjuvants? *Arthritis Rheum (2002)* 47(5):543-5 10.1002/art.10666 PMID: 12382305.

1079 102 - Guis S, Pellissier JF, Nicoli F, Reviron D, Mattei JP, Gherardi RK, et al. HLA-DRB1*01 and
1080 macrophagic myofasciitis. *Arthritis Rheum (2002)* 46(9):2535-7 10.1002/art.10465 PMID:
1081 12355502.

1082 103 - Amoura Z, Costedoat N, Maisonobe T, Godeau P, Piette JC. Familial macrophagic
1083 myofasciitis. *Ann Rheum Dis (2000)* 59(11):927-8 10.1136/ard.59.11.926b PMID: 11203423

1084 104 - Nevo Y, Kutai M, Jossiphov J, Livne A, Neeman Z, Arad T, et al. Childhood macrophagic
1085 myofasciitis-consanguinity and clinicopathological features. *Neuromuscul Disord (2004)*
1086 14(4):246-52. 10.1016/j.nmd.2003.12.005 PMID: 15019702.

- 1087 105 - Brissot P, Pietrangelo A, Adams PC, de Graaff B, McLaren CE, Loréal O.
1088 Haemochromatosis. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2018 Apr 5;4:18016. doi: 10.1038/nrdp.2018.16.
1089 PMID: 29620054
- 1090 106 - Mayr R, Janecke AR, Schranz M, Griffiths WJ, Vogel W, Pietrangelo A, Zoller H.
1091 Ferroportin disease: a systematic meta-analysis of clinical and molecular findings. *J Hepatol*.
1092 2010 Nov;53(5):941-9. doi: 10.1016/j.jhep.2010.05.016. Epub 2010 Jul 17. Erratum in: *J*
1093 *Hepatol*. 2011 Sep;55(3):734-736. doi: 10.1016/j.jhep.2011.05.002. PMID: 20691492
- 1094 107 - Zhang Y, Zou L, Li X, Guo L, Hu B, Ye H, Liu Y. SLC40A1 in iron metabolism, ferroptosis,
1095 and disease: A review. *WIREs Mech Dis*. 2024 Jul-Aug;16(4):e1644. doi: 10.1002/wsbm.1644.
1096 Epub 2024 Mar 20. PMID: 38508867
- 1097 108 - Kevin Uguen, Chandran Ka, Gwenaëlle Collod-Bérout, Marlène Le Tertre, Julie Guellec,
1098 et al.. The Spectra of Disease-Causing Mutations in the Ferroportin 1 (SLC40A1) Encoding
1099 Gene and Related Iron Overload Phenotypes (Hemochromatosis Type 4 and Ferroportin
1100 Disease). *Human Mutation*, 2023, 2023, pp.1 - 22. ff10.1155/2023/5162256ff. fhal-04241559
1101 doi.org/10.1155/2023/5162256
- 1102 109 - Vlasveld LT, Janssen R, Bardou-Jacquet E, Venselaar H, Hamdi-Roze H, Drakesmith H,
1103 Swinkels DW. Twenty Years of Ferroportin Disease: A Review or An Update of Published
1104 Clinical, Biochemical, Molecular, and Functional Features. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel)*. 2019 Sep
1105 9;12(3):132. doi: 10.3390/ph12030132. PMID: 31505869
- 1106 110 - Raszaja-Wyszomirska J, Caleffi A, Milkiewicz P, Pietrangelo A. Ferroportin-related
1107 haemochromatosis associated with novel Y64H mutation of the SCL40A1 gene. *Prz*
1108 *Gastroenterol*. 2014;9(5):307-9. doi: 10.5114/pg.2014.46167. PMID: 25396007
- 1109 111 - Silvia Majore, Maria Carmela Bonaccorsi di Patti, Michele Valiante, Fabio Politicelli,
1110 Andrea Cortese, Sabrina Di Bartolomeo, Carmelilia De Bernardo, Marianna De Muro, Fiorella
1111 Faienza, Francesca Clementina Radio, Paola Grammatico, Giovanni Musci, Characterization of
1112 three novel pathogenic SLC40A1 mutations and genotype/phenotype correlations in 7 Italian
1113 families with type 4 hereditary hemochromatosis, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) -*
1114 *Molecular Basis of Disease*, Volume 1864, Issue 2, 2018, Pages 464-470, ISSN 0925-4439,
1115 doi.org/10.1016/j.bbadis.2017.11.006. PMID: 29154924.
- 1116 112 - Johnson EE, Sandgren A, Cherayil BJ, Murray M, Wessling-Resnick M. Role of ferroportin
1117 in macrophage-mediated immunity. *Infect Immun*. 2010 Dec;78(12):5099-106. doi:
1118 10.1128/IAI.00498-10. PMID: 20837712
- 1119 113 - Yu Peng, Junqin Yang, Zedong Li, Sheng Chen, Xianming Tang, Jun Zhou, Overexpression
1120 of SLC40A1 inhibits the malignancy of hepatocellular carcinoma MHCC-97H cells by
1121 stimulation of autophagy, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, Volume 75, 2022,
1122 103554, ISSN 1746-8094, doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2022.103554.
- 1123 114 - Gherardi RK, Crépeaux G, Authier FJ. Myalgia and chronic fatigue syndrome following
1124 immunization: macrophagic myofasciitis and animal studies support linkage to aluminum

1125 adjuvant persistency and diffusion in the immune system. *Autoimmun Rev.* 2019
1126 Jul;18(7):691-705. doi: 10.1016/j.autrev.2019.05.006. PMID: 31059838.

1127 115 - Eidi H, David MO, Crépeaux G, Henry L, Joshi V, Berger MH, Sennour M, Cadusseau J,
1128 Gherardi RK, Curmi PA. Fluorescent nanodiamonds as a relevant tag for the assessment of
1129 alum adjuvant particle biodisposition. *BMC Med.* 2015 Jun 17;13:144. doi: 10.1186/s12916-
1130 015-0388-2. PMID: 26082187

1131 116 - Khan Z, Combadière C, Authier FJ, Itier V, Lux F, Exley C, Mahrouf-Yorgov M, Decrouy X,
1132 Moretto P, Tillement O, Gherardi RK, Cadusseau J. Slow CCL2-dependent translocation of
1133 biopersistent particles from muscle to brain. *BMC Med.* 2013 Apr 4;11:99. doi:
1134 10.1186/1741-7015-11-99. PMID: 23557144

1135 117 - Crépeaux G, Eidi H, David MO, Tzavara E, Giros B, Exley C, Curmi PA, Shaw CA, Gherardi
1136 RK, Cadusseau J. Highly delayed systemic translocation of aluminum-based adjuvant in CD1
1137 mice following intramuscular injections. *J Inorg Biochem.* 2015 Nov;152:199-205. doi:
1138 10.1016/j.jinorgbio.2015.07.004. PMID: 26384437.

1139 118 - Common conditions associated with hereditary haemochromatosis genetic variants:
1140 cohort study in UK Biobank. *BMJ.* 2019 Oct 23;367:l6157. doi: 10.1136/bmj.l6157. Erratum
1141 for: *BMJ.* 2019 Jan 16;364:k5222. doi: 10.1136/bmj.k5222. PMID: 31645331

1142 119 - Gregory A, Lotia M, Jeong SY, Fox R, Zhen D, Sanford L, Hamada J, Jahic A, Beetz C,
1143 Freed A, Kurian MA, Cullup T, van der Weijden MCM, Nguyen V, Setthavongsack N, Garcia D,
1144 Krajbich V, Pham T, Woltjer R, George BP, Minks KQ, Paciorkowski AR, Hogarth P, Jankovic J,
1145 Hayflick SJ. Autosomal dominant mitochondrial membrane protein-associated
1146 neurodegeneration (MPAN). *Mol Genet Genomic Med.* 2019 Jul;7(7):e00736. doi:
1147 10.1002/mgg3.736. PMID: 31087512

1148 120 - Ward RJ, Zucca FA, Duyn JH, Crichton RR, Zecca L. The role of iron in brain ageing and
1149 neurodegenerative disorders. *Lancet Neurol.* 2014 Oct;13(10):1045-60. doi: 10.1016/S1474-
1150 4422(14)70117-6. PMID: 25231526

1151 121 - Rhodes SL, Buchanan DD, Ahmed I, Taylor KD, Lorient MA, Sinsheimer JS, Bronstein JM,
1152 Elbaz A, Mellick GD, Rotter JI, Ritz B. Pooled analysis of iron-related genes in Parkinson's
1153 disease: association with transferrin. *Neurobiol Dis.* 2014 Feb;62:172-8. doi:
1154 10.1016/j.nbd.2013.09.019. Epub 2013 Oct 8. PMID: 24121126

1155 122 - Fei Y, Ding Y. The role of ferroptosis in neurodegenerative diseases. *Front Cell Neurosci.*
1156 2024 Oct 15;18:1475934. doi: 10.3389/fncel.2024.1475934. PMID: 39473490

1157 123 - Dusek, P., Schneider, S. A., and Aaseth, J. (2016). Iron chelation in the treatment of
1158 neurodegenerative diseases. *J. Trace Elem. Med. Biol.* 38, 81–92. doi:
1159 10.1016/j.jtemb.2016.03.010 PMID: 27033472.

1160 124 - Munkholm K, Jacoby AS, Vinberg M, Kessing LV. Ferritin as a potential disease marker in
1161 patients with bipolar disorder. *J Affect Disord.* 2023 Jul 1;332:247-253. doi:
1162 10.1016/j.jad.2023.04.006. PMID: 37037316.

1163 125 - Lotan A, Luza S, Opazo CM, Ayton S, Lane DJR, Mancuso S, Pereira A, Sundram S,
1164 Weickert CS, Bousman C, Pantelis C, Everall IP, Bush AI. Perturbed iron biology in the
1165 prefrontal cortex of people with schizophrenia. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2023 May;28(5):2058-2070.
1166 doi: 10.1038/s41380-023-01979-3. PMID: 36750734

1167 126 - Chen MH, Su TP, Chen YS, Hsu JW, Huang KL, Chang WH, Chen TJ, Bai YM. Association
1168 between psychiatric disorders and iron deficiency anemia among children and adolescents: a
1169 nationwide population-based study. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2013 Jun 4;13:161. doi: 10.1186/1471-
1170 244X-13-161. PMID: 23735056

1171 127 - Duță C, Muscurel C, Dogaru CB, Stoian I. Ferroptosis-A Shared Mechanism for
1172 Parkinson's Disease and Type 2 Diabetes. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2024 Aug 14;25(16):8838. doi:
1173 10.3390/ijms25168838. PMID: 39201524

1174 128 - Paola Dongiovanni, Massimiliano Ruscica, Raffaella Rametta, Stefania Recalcati, Liliana
1175 Steffani, Stefano Gatti, Domenico Girelli, Gaetano Cairo, Paolo Magni, Silvia Fargion, Luca
1176 Valenti, Dietary Iron Overload Induces Visceral Adipose Tissue Insulin Resistance, *The*
1177 *American Journal of Pathology*, Volume 182, Issue 6, 2013, Pages 2254-2263, ISSN 0002-
1178 9440, doi.org/10.1016/j.ajpath.2013.02.019. PMID: 23578384.

1179 129 - Kong, Y., Hu, L., Lu, K. et al. Ferroportin downregulation promotes cell proliferation by
1180 modulating the Nrf2–miR-17-5p axis in multiple myeloma. *Cell Death Dis* 10, 624 (2019).
1181 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41419-019-1854-0>

1182 130 - Rabaya S, Nairat S, Bader K, Herzallah MM, Darwish HM. Iron metabolism in autism
1183 spectrum disorder; inference through single nucleotide polymorphisms in key iron
1184 metabolism genes. *J Neurol Sci*. 2023 Oct 15;453:120817. doi: 10.1016/j.jns.2023.120817..
1185 PMID: 37813049.

1186 131 - Chen L, Guo X, Hou C, Tang P, Zhang X, Chong L, Li R. The causal association between
1187 iron status and the risk of autism: A Mendelian randomization study. *Front Nutr*. 2022 Nov
1188 3;9:957600. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2022.957600. PMID: 36407516

1189 132 - Abha Chauhan, Ved Chauhan, Oxidative stress in autism, *Pathophysiology*, Volume 13,
1190 Issue 3, 2006, Pages 171-181, ISSN 0928-4680,
1191 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pathophys.2006.05.007>. PMID: 16766163.

1192 133 - Chauhan A, Chauhan V, Brown WT, Cohen I. Oxidative stress in autism: increased lipid
1193 peroxidation and reduced serum levels of ceruloplasmin and transferrin-the antioxidant
1194 proteins. *Life Sci*. (2004) 75:2539–49. 10.1016/j.lfs.2004.04.038 PMID: 15363659.

1195 134 - Azmerin M, Hussain MdS, Aziz MdA, et al. TF and TCF4 gene polymorphisms are linked
1196 to autism spectrum disorder: a case–control study. *Journal of International Medical*
1197 *Research*. 2022;50(11). doi:10.1177/03000605221138492 PMID: 36448207

1198 135 - Chen L, Guo X, Hou C, Tang P, Zhang X, Chong L, Li R. The causal association between
1199 iron status and the risk of autism: A Mendelian randomization study. *Front Nutr*. 2022 Nov
1200 3;9:957600. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2022.957600. PMID: 36407516

1201 136 - Department of Health (Northern Ireland). Publication of 'The Prevalence of Autism
1202 (including Aspergers Syndrome) in School Age Children in Northern Ireland. Annual Report
1203 2023'. Belfast: Department of Health; 2023 [cited 2024 Apr 30]. Available from:
1204 [https://www.health-ni.gov.uk/news/publication-prevalence-autism-including-aspergers-](https://www.health-ni.gov.uk/news/publication-prevalence-autism-including-aspergers-syndrome-school-age-children-northern-ireland-annual-report-2023)
1205 [syndrome-school-age-children-northern-ireland-annual-report-2023](https://www.health-ni.gov.uk/news/publication-prevalence-autism-including-aspergers-syndrome-school-age-children-northern-ireland-annual-report-2023)

1206 137 - Tallaght University Hospital. Hereditary Haemochromatosis [Internet]. Dublin: Tallaght
1207 University Hospital; [cited 2024 Apr 30]. Available from:
1208 <https://www.tuh.ie/Departments/Gastroenterology/Hereditary-Haemochromatosis.html>

1209 138 - Lukiw WJ, Kruck TPA, Percy ME, Pogue AI, Alexandrov PN, Walsh WJ, Sharfman NM,
1210 Jaber VR, Zhao Y, Li W, Bergeron C, Culicchia F, Fang Z, McLachlan DRC. Aluminum in
1211 neurological disease - a 36 year multicenter study. *J Alzheimers Dis Parkinsonism*.
1212 2019;8(6):457. doi: 10.4172/2161-0460.1000457. PMID: 31179161

1213 139 – Tomljenovic L, Shaw CA. Mechanisms of aluminum adjuvant toxicity and autoimmunity
1214 in pediatric populations. *Lupus*. 2012 Feb;21(2):223-30. doi: 10.1177/0961203311430221.
1215 PMID: 22235057.

1216 140 - Rouault TA. Mitochondrial iron overload: causes and consequences. *Curr Opin Genet
1217 Dev*. 2016 Jun;38:31-37. doi: 10.1016/j.gde.2016.02.004. PMID: 27026139

1218 141 - Exley, C., Clarkson, E. Aluminium in human brain tissue from donors without
1219 neurodegenerative disease: A comparison with Alzheimer's disease, multiple sclerosis and
1220 autism. *Sci Rep* 10, 7770 (2020). doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-64734-6 PMID: 32385326

1221 142 - Alberto Boretti, Reviewing the association between aluminum adjuvants in the vaccines
1222 and autism spectrum disorder, *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*, Volume
1223 66, 2021, 126764, ISSN 0946-672X, doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2021.126764. PMID: 33930617

1224 143 - Yumoto S, Kakimi S, Ishikawa A. Colocalization of Aluminum and Iron in Nuclei of Nerve
1225 Cells in Brains of Patients with Alzheimer's Disease. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2018;65(4):1267-1281.
1226 doi: 10.3233/JAD-171108. PMID: 30149443

1227 144 - De Sole P, Rossi C, Chiarpotto M, Ciasca G, Bocca B, Alimonti A, Bizzarro A, Rossi C,
1228 Masullo C. Possible relationship between Al/ferritin complex and Alzheimer's disease. *Clin
1229 Biochem*. 2013 Jan;46(1-2):89-93. doi: 10.1016/j.clinbiochem.2012.10.023. PMID: 23103708

1230 145 - Walter PB, Knutson MD, Paler-Martinez A, Lee S, Xu Y, Viteri FE, Ames BN. Iron
1231 deficiency and iron excess damage mitochondria and mitochondrial DNA in rats. *Proc Natl
1232 Acad Sci U S A*. 2002 Feb 19;99(4):2264-9. doi: 10.1073/pnas.261708798. PMID: 11854522

1233 146 - Xu J, Marzetti E, Seo AY, Kim JS, Prolla TA, Leeuwenburgh C. The emerging role of iron
1234 dyshomeostasis in the mitochondrial decay of aging. *Mech Ageing Dev*. 2010 Jul-Aug;131(7-
1235 8):487-93. doi: 10.1016/j.mad.2010.04.007. PMID: 20434480

1236 147 - Su X, Wang G, Liu S, Li J, Shao M, Yang Y, Song M, Han Y, Li W, Lv L. Autophagy defects at
1237 weaning impair complement-dependent synaptic pruning and induce behavior deficits. *J*

1238 Neuroinflammation. 2024 Sep 27;21(1):239. doi: 10.1186/s12974-024-03235-z. PMID:
1239 39334475

1240 148 - Tomoda T, Yang K, Sawa A. Neuronal Autophagy in Synaptic Functions and Psychiatric
1241 Disorders. *Biol Psychiatry*. 2020 May 1;87(9):787-796. doi: 10.1016/j.biopsych.2019.07.018.
1242 PMID: 31542152

1243 149 - Tang G, Gudsnuk K, Kuo SH, Cotrina ML, Rosoklija G, Sosunov A, Sonders MS, Kanter E,
1244 Castagna C, Yamamoto A, Yue Z, Arancio O, Peterson BS, Champagne F, Dwork AJ, Goldman J,
1245 Sulzer D. Loss of mTOR-dependent macroautophagy causes autistic-like synaptic pruning
1246 deficits. *Neuron*. 2014 Sep 3;83(5):1131-43. doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2014.07.040. Erratum in:
1247 *Neuron*. 2014 Sep 17;83(6):1482. PMID: 25155956

1248 150 - Angrand L, Masson J-D, Rubio-Casillas A, Nosten-Bertrand M, Crépeaux G.
1249 Inflammation and Autophagy: A Convergent Point between Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)-
1250 Related Genetic and Environmental Factors: Focus on Aluminum Adjuvants. *Toxics*. 2022;
1251 10(9):518. doi.org/10.3390/toxics10090518 PMID: 36136483

1252 151 - Cortes M, Cao M, Liu HL, Moore CS, Durosier LD, Burns P, Fecteau G, Desrochers A,
1253 Barreiro LB, Antel JP, Frasch MG. $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptor signaling modulates the
1254 inflammatory phenotype of fetal brain microglia: first evidence of interference by iron
1255 homeostasis. *Sci Rep*. 2017 Sep 6;7(1):10645. doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-09439-z. PMID:
1256 28878260

1257 152 - Zimmermann P, Antonelli MC, Sharma R, Müller A, Zelgert C, Fabre B, Wenzel N, Wu HT,
1258 Frasch MG, Lobmaier SM. Prenatal stress perturbs fetal iron homeostasis in a sex specific
1259 manner. *Sci Rep*. 2022 Jun 4;12(1):9341. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-13633-z. PMID: 35662279

1260 153 - Loréal O, Cavey T, Bardou-Jacquet E, Guggenbuhl P, Ropert M, Brissot P. Iron, hepcidin,
1261 and the metal connection. *Front Pharmacol*. 2014 Jun 4;5:128. doi:
1262 10.3389/fphar.2014.00128. PMID: 24926268

1263 154 - Elsa Delaby. Dissection de l'architecture génétique de l'autisme par analyse des
1264 variations du nombre de copies de gènes. *Neurosciences [q-bio.NC]*. Université Pierre et
1265 Marie Curie - Paris VI, 2014. Français. ffNNT : 2014PA066242ff. fftel-01086685

1266 155 - Rabaya S, Nairat S, Bader K, Herzallah MM, Darwish HM. Iron metabolism in autism
1267 spectrum disorder; inference through single nucleotide polymorphisms in key iron
1268 metabolism genes. *J Neurol Sci*. 2023 Oct 15;453:120817. doi: 10.1016/j.jns.2023.120817.
1269 Epub 2023 Sep 25. PMID: 37813049.

1270 156 - Chen L, Guo X, Hou C, Tang P, Zhang X, Chong L, Li R. The causal association between
1271 iron status and the risk of autism: A Mendelian randomization study. *Front Nutr*. 2022 Nov
1272 3;9:957600. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2022.957600. PMID: 36407516

1273 157 - Azmerin M, Hussain MdS, Aziz MdA, et al. TF and TCF4 gene polymorphisms are linked
1274 to autism spectrum disorder: a case–control study. *Journal of International Medical
1275 Research*. 2022;50(11). doi:10.1177/03000605221138492 PMID: 36448207

1276 158 - Santos PC, Dinardo CL, Cançado RD, Schettert IT, Krieger JE, Pereira AC. Non-HFE
1277 hemochromatosis. *Rev Bras Hematol Hemoter.* 2012;34(4):311-6. doi: 10.5581/1516-
1278 8484.20120079. PMID: 23049448

1279 159 - Wallace, D., Subramaniam, V. The global prevalence of HFE and non-HFE
1280 hemochromatosis estimated from analysis of next-generation sequencing data. *Genet Med*
1281 18, 618–626 (2016). doi.org/10.1038/gim.2015.140 PMID: 26633544.

1282 160 - Anderson GJ, Bardou-Jacquet E. Revisiting hemochromatosis: genetic vs. phenotypic
1283 manifestations. *Ann Transl Med.* 2021 Apr;9(8):731. doi: 10.21037/atm-20-5512. PMID:
1284 33987429

1285 161 - Rombout-Sestrienkova E, Nieman FH, Essers BA, van Noord PA, Janssen MC, van
1286 Deursen CT, Bos LP, Rombout F, van den Braak R, de Leeuw PW, Koek GH. Erythrocytapheresis
1287 versus phlebotomy in the initial treatment of HFE hemochromatosis patients: results from a
1288 randomized trial. *Transfusion.* 2012 Mar;52(3):470-7. doi: 10.1111/j.1537-
1289 2995.2011.03292.x. PMID: 21848963.

1290 162 - Nishina S, Tomiyama Y, Ikuta K, Tatsumi Y, Toki Y, Kato A, Kato K, Yoshioka N, Sasaki K,
1291 Hara Y, Hino K. Long-term phlebotomy successfully alleviated hepatic iron accumulation in a
1292 ferroportin disease patient with a mutation in SLC40A1: a case report. *BMC Gastroenterol.*
1293 2021 Mar 5;21(1):111. doi: 10.1186/s12876-021-01674-z. PMID: 33673803

1294 163 - Pietrangelo A. Ferroportin disease: pathogenesis, diagnosis and treatment.
1295 *Haematologica.* 2017 Dec;102(12):1972-1984. doi: 10.3324/haematol.2017.170720. PMID:
1296 29101207

1297 164 - Krishan S, Jansson PJ, Gutierrez E, Lane DJ, Richardson D, Sahni S. IRON METABOLISM
1298 AND AUTOPHAGY: A POORLY EXPLORED RELATIONSHIP THAT HAS IMPORTANT
1299 CONSEQUENCES FOR HEALTH AND DISEASE. *Nagoya J Med Sci.* 2015 Feb;77(1-2):1-6. PMID:
1300 25797965

1301 165 - Kotajima-Murakami H, Kobayashi T, Kashii H, Sato A, Hagino Y, Tanaka M, Nishito Y,
1302 Takamatsu Y, Uchino S, Ikeda K. Effects of rapamycin on social interaction deficits and gene
1303 expression in mice exposed to valproic acid in utero. *Mol Brain.* 2019 Jan 8;12(1):3. doi:
1304 10.1186/s13041-018-0423-2. PMID: 30621732

1305 166 - Carosi JM, Sargeant TJ. Rapamycin and Alzheimer disease: a double-edged sword?
1306 *Autophagy.* 2019 Aug;15(8):1460-1462. doi: 10.1080/15548627.2019.1615823. PMID:
1307 31066320

1308 167 - Gherardi RK, Coquet M, Cherin P, Belec L, Moretto P, Dreyfus PA, Pellissier JF, Chariot P,
1309 Authier FJ. Macrophagic myofasciitis lesions assess long-term persistence of vaccine-derived
1310 aluminium hydroxide in muscle. *Brain.* 2001 Sep;124(Pt 9):1821-31. doi:
1311 10.1093/brain/124.9.1821. PMID: 11522584.

1312 168 - Martinez-Morata I, Sobel M, Tellez-Plaza M, Navas-Acien A, Howe CG, Sanchez TR. A
1313 State-of-the-Science Review on Metal Biomarkers. *Curr Environ Health Rep.* 2023
1314 Sep;10(3):215-249. doi: 10.1007/s40572-023-00402-x. PMID: 37337116

1315 169 - Bao WD, Pang P, Zhou XT, Hu F, Xiong W, Chen K, Wang J, Wang F, Xie D, Hu YZ, Han ZT,
1316 Zhang HH, Wang WX, Nelson PT, Chen JG, Lu Y, Man HY, Liu D, Zhu LQ. Loss of ferroportin
1317 induces memory impairment by promoting ferroptosis in Alzheimer's disease. *Cell Death*
1318 *Differ.* 2021 May;28(5):1548-1562. doi: 10.1038/s41418-020-00685-9. Erratum in: *Cell Death*
1319 *Differ.* 2024 Aug;31(8):1099. doi: 10.1038/s41418-024-01290-w. PMID: 33398092

1320 170 - Susan J. Hayflick, Manju A. Kurian, Penelope Hogarth, Chapter 19 - Neurodegeneration
1321 with brain iron accumulation, Editor(s): Daniel H. Geschwind, Henry L. Paulson, Christine
1322 Klein, *Handbook of Clinical Neurology*, Elsevier, Volume 147, 2018, Pages 293-305, ISSN 0072-
1323 9752, ISBN 9780444632333, doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63233-3.00019-1. PMID:
1324 29325618

1325 171 - Mobarra N, Shanaki M, Ehteram H, Nasiri H, Sahmani M, Saeidi M, Goudarzi M,
1326 Pourkarim H, Azad M. A Review on Iron Chelators in Treatment of Iron Overload Syndromes.
1327 *Int J Hematol Oncol Stem Cell Res.* 2016 Oct 1;10(4):239-247. PMID: 27928480

1328 172 - Barney E. Dwyer, Leo R. Zacharski, Dominic J. Balestra, Alan J. Lerner, George Perry,
1329 Xiongwei Zhu, Mark A. Smith, Getting the iron out: Phlebotomy for Alzheimer's disease?,
1330 *Medical Hypotheses*, Volume 72, Issue 5, 2009, Pages 504-509, ISSN 0306-9877,
1331 doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2008.12.029. PMID: 19195795

1332 173 – Pilling LC, Tamosauskaite J, Jones G, Wood AR, Jones L, Kuo CL, Kuchel GA, Ferrucci L,
1333 Melzer D. Common conditions associated with hereditary haemochromatosis genetic
1334 variants: cohort study in UK Biobank. *BMJ.* 2019 Jan 16;364:k5222. doi: 10.1136/bmj.k5222.
1335 Erratum in: *BMJ.* 2019 Oct 23;367:l6157. doi: 10.1136/bmj.l6157. PMID: 30651232

1336 174 – European Association For The Study Of The Liver. EASL clinical practice guidelines for
1337 HFE hemochromatosis. *J Hepatol.* 2010 Jul;53(1):3-22. doi: 10.1016/j.jhep.2010.03.001.
1338 PMID: 20471131.

1339 175 – Hollerer I, Bachmann A, Muckenthaler MU. Pathophysiological consequences and
1340 benefits of HFE mutations: 20 years of research. *Haematologica.* 2017 May;102(5):809-817.
1341 doi: 10.3324/haematol.2016.160432. Epub 2017 Mar 9. PMID: 28280078

1342 176 - Lucas MR, Atkins JL, Pilling LC, Shearman JD, Melzer D. HFE genotypes,
1343 haemochromatosis diagnosis and clinical outcomes at age 80 years: a prospective cohort
1344 study in the UK Biobank. *BMJ Open.* 2024 Mar 13;14(3):e081926. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-
1345 2023-081926. PMID: 38479735

1346 177 - Wallace, D., Subramaniam, V. The global prevalence of HFE and non-HFE
1347 hemochromatosis estimated from analysis of next-generation sequencing data. *Genet Med*
1348 18, 618–626 (2016). doi.org/10.1038/gim.2015.140 PMID: 26633544.

1349 178 - Aleksandar Ćirović, Ana Ćirović, Dimitrije Nikolić, Ana Ivanovski, Petar Ivanovski, The
1350 adjuvant aluminum fate – Metabolic tale based on the basics of chemistry and biochemistry,
1351 *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*, Volume 68, 2021, 126822, ISSN 0946-
1352 672X, doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2021.126822. PMID: 34333362.

1353 179 - Delatycki MB, Allen KJ. Population Screening for Hereditary Haemochromatosis-Should
1354 It Be Carried Out, and If So, How? *Genes* (Basel). 2024 Jul 23;15(8):967. doi:
1355 10.3390/genes15080967. PMID: 39202328

1356 180 - Cirovic A, Cirovic A. Aluminum bone toxicity in infants may be promoted by iron
1357 deficiency. *J Trace Elem Med Biol*. 2022 May;71:126941. doi: 10.1016/j.jtemb.2022.126941.
1358 Epub 2022 Jan 31. PMID: 35123368.

1359 181 - Barton JC, Barton JC. Dupuytren's Contracture in Alabama HFE Hemochromatosis
1360 Probands. *Clin Med Insights Arthritis Musculoskelet Disord*. 2012;5:67-75. doi:
1361 10.4137/CMAMD.S9935. PMID: 22952417

1362 182 - Flatt AE. The Vikings and Baron Dupuytren's disease. *Proc (Bayl Univ Med Cent)*. 2001
1363 Oct;14(4):378-84. doi: 10.1080/08998280.2001.11927791. PMID: 16369649

1364 183 - Jónsson T, Gudmundsson KG, Bjarnadóttir K, Hjalmsardótti IB, Gudmundsson S,
1365 Arngrímsson R. Association of HLA-DRB1*01 with Dupuytren's disease. *Scand J Rheumatol*.
1366 2013;42(1):45-7. doi: 10.3109/03009742.2012.713982. PMID: 22991974.

1367 184 - Tomljenovic L, Shaw CA. Aluminum vaccine adjuvants: are they safe? *Curr Med Chem*.
1368 2011;18(17):2630-7. doi: 10.2174/092986711795933740. PMID: 21568886.

1369 185 - PITTMAN M, COX CB. PERTUSSIS VACCINE TESTING FOR FREEDOM-FROM-TOXICITY.
1370 *Appl Microbiol*. 1965 May;13(3):447-56. doi: 10.1128/am.13.3.447-456.1965. PMID:
1371 14325286

1372 186 - Masson, J. D., Angrand, L., Badran, G., de Miguel, R., & Crépeaux, G. (2022). Clearance,
1373 biodistribution, and neuromodulatory effects of aluminum-based adjuvants. *Systematic*
1374 *review and meta-analysis: what do we learn from animal studies?* *Critical Reviews in*
1375 *Toxicology*, 52(6), 403–419. doi.org/10.1080/10408444.2022.2105688 PMID: 36112128.

1376 187 - Kumar A, Sharma E, Marley A, Samaan MA, Brookes MJ. Iron deficiency anaemia:
1377 pathophysiology, assessment, practical management. *BMJ Open Gastroenterol*. 2022
1378 Jan;9(1):e000759. doi: 10.1136/bmjgast-2021-000759. PMID: 34996762

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